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ANNUAL REPORT

OF THE

ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT

GWALIOR STATE

FOR

Samvat 1984, Year 1927-28.

~~1927-28~~
Gwalior

GWALIOR
ALIJAH DARBAR PRESS,—LASHKAR.

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ANNUAL REPORT

OF THE

ARCHAEOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT

GWALIOR STATE

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF
THE DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY, GWALIOR STATE,
FOR
The Year ending 30th June 1928, Samvat 1984.

PART I.

I. Office Notes.

Charge.—The undersigned held charge of the Department during the year of report except for a period of two months and twenty-eight days of privilege leave, which he availed himself of at three different occasions in the year. During the period of leave, the charge of current duties of the post remained with Mr. R. S. Saksena, the Archæological Inspector.

2. *Leave.*—Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows:—

- (1) *Inspector.*—Privilege leave for twelve days.
- (2) *Photographer-draughtsman.*—Privilege leave for twenty-one days, sick leave for twenty days and leave without pay for one month and eighteen days.
- (3) *Officer Correspondence.*—Privilege leave for four days.
- (4) *Record-keeper.*—Privilege leave for twenty-four days and sick leave for one month and twenty-two days.

3. *Appointments and Promotions.*—There were no new appointments or promotions during the year of report. But V M. Shavrikar, Assistant Photographer-draughtsman, and Sukhram Thakore, Curator, Archæological Museum, appointed on probation last year, were confirmed.

II. Administrative Changes and Orders.

4. This Department was reverted from the 'Public Works Portfolio' to the 'Home Portfolio', the former having been abolished from the 1st January 1928.

5. No Circular or Departmental Order with special reference to this Department was issued in the year of report.

6. *General.*—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently, and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

III. Work at Headquarters.

7. In addition to the ordinary routine of office, the following work was done during the headquarters season :—

- (a) The *Annual Administration Report* for Samvat 1983 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were classified, arranged and labelled.
- (c) A *Guide to the Museum of Archæology at Gwalior* was prepared and published.
- (d) A brochure in Marathi, containing brief notes on places of archæological and historical interest at Lashkar, Gwalior and Morar and the neighbourhood was drafted at the request of 'Sri Madhava Marathi Vanmaya Mandala of Gwalior' for the use of the guests of the All-India Marathi Sahitya Sammelana, which was held at Gwalior in the month of April of the year of report.
- (e) A set of enlarged photographs was supplied to the Shivpuri Hotel, for exhibition, with a view to attract travellers to visit our monuments.
- (f) Arrangements were made with the Publicity Superintendent, G. I. P. Railway, to exhibit enlarged photographs of some important Archæological monuments in the State, at the Victoria Terminus, Bombay, Khandwa, Ujjain and Sanchi stations on the G. I. P. Railway for arousing interest in the travelling public to see the relics.
- (g) Albums of select Archæological monuments with short descriptive labels were prepared and presented to the Members of the States Enquiry Committee, on the occasion of their visit to Gwalior.
- (h) The coins received as treasure-trove finds or offered for sale or exchange by private bodies and individuals were examined and listed.
- (i) An article on a Persian-Arabic inscription and another on a Persian inscription at Ujjain were contributed to the *Indian Antiquary*. A third article on a Persian-Arabic inscription at Udaypur was contributed to the *Indian Historical Quarterly*.
- (j) The third edition of the *Gwalior Fort Album* was published.

IV. Tours.

8. During the year of report, the Superintendent and the Officiating Superintendent spent 82 and 7 days respectively in camp, partly for

the annual inspection of monuments already conserved, for supervising and directing works of conservation in progress, for preparing estimates of conservation works intended to be undertaken and partly for listing monuments. The detailed diary of the tour will be found in Appendix A.

9. The Superintendent paid visits of annual inspection to the monuments at Suhania, Ranod, Chanderi, Narwar, Surwaya, Bhilsa, Gwalior, Udaygiri, Ujjain, Mandasaur, Sondni and Bagh. He supervised and directed the conservation works in progress at Gwalior, Antri, Narwar, Surwaya, Udaygiri and Bagh. He visited Kadwaha, Terahi, Chanderi, Udaygiri and Kashipur for preparing estimates of conservation works to be undertaken, and Karera, Dinara, Narwar, Sakarra, Anghora and Ramesvar for listing ancient monuments.

10. Moreover the Superintendent visited two places outside the State, namely, (1) Devaguradia near Indore and (2) Nagari near Chitorgarh. The object and result of these visits are briefly described on pages 26 and 27 below.

V. Conservation.

11. Conservation was carried out at Bagh, Udaygiri, Narwar, Surwaya, Suhania, Antri and Gwalior at a total cost of Rs. 17,684-4-11 including the special grants for Narwar Fort and Bagh Caves.

12. The statement of monuments conserved in the year under report is set forth in Appendix B.

13. *Bagh* (District Amjhera).—The special grant allotted for the partial conservation of the Buddhist Caves at Bagh last year (Samvat 1983) which could not be spent in that year owing to the late receipt of the sanction as noted in the last year's *Annual Report* was utilised in the year of report. Further progress was made in the clearance of the dark cells of cave No. 2. This item is being done from time to time during the past two years.

14. Of all the caves worth preserving in this group cave No. 4 is the most interesting as also most exposed to danger. As such it had the first claim on our attention. The special grant was therefore put to the service of this cave. The allotment was however not enough for putting the whole cave in a safe condition; only partial conservation could therefore be carried out. The work consisted chiefly in providing supports to the ceiling of the cave which was in a perilous condition owing to most of the original pillars having either disappeared altogether or having been weakened by partial decay, resulting from the fragile condition of the rock and the effect of age. From the same causes large portions of the walls have been undermined at the bases and these had to be underpinned.

15. Seven pillars and two pilasters which had been damaged in parts were repaired and ten new pillars were constructed in the place of those that had disappeared. Underpinning was confined chiefly to the front walls of caves Nos. 2 and 4. The general design of the

original pillars has been copied in the construction of new pillars. In repairing decayed pillars and underpinning walls the decayed portion of the rock was carefully cut out and new masonry of dressed stone in cement mortar was substituted. The masonry of newly constructed pillars is made up of an outer casing of finely dressed blocks of stone with an infilling of cement concrete. Good building stone is very rare in the locality. So all stone masonry was not employed as being more costly and less strong. Pillars wholly made of cement concrete may perhaps have been stronger but that device had also to be rejected as being out of keeping with the nature of an ancient monument. A middle course was therefore adopted as being the best as regards economy, strength and appearance. The suggestions of Mr. Jugal Kishore Vaishya, District Engineer, P. W. D., who was consulted in this connection, were found to be eminently practical and useful, for which our thanks are due to him.

16. Subsequent to the first clearance of the cave a portion of the ceiling had collapsed. This fresh debris was removed with an exception of a few blocks which bear traces of painting on their surface. It is intended to saw out pieces of this painted surface and preserve them in the Archaeological Museum.

17. In order to protect the valuable paintings on the outside of caves Nos. 4 and 5 it was first proposed to erect a sort of shed. But this proposal was later on abandoned in favour of teak wood frames with shutters. The shed was found to be superfluous as no direct rain could reach the painted wall, the damaged roof of the verandah above serving as a sort of *chhajja*. Owing to the late approval of the design of the framing, this item could not be carried out in the year of report. It will be done early next season.

18. Much more conservation work awaits being done in cave No. 4 and also other caves, but it will be done gradually as funds permit. For the present, temporary supports have been set up where necessary to prop up overhanging ceilings and cracked lintels of doorways and window openings.

19. A finely drawn but badly damaged painting was exposed to view after the removal of debris flanking the southern side of the entrance to the *dagoba* chapel in cave No. 4. As the painted surface here is in a precarious condition and as there is no knowing what moment it may drop away, the painting was copied in full size in the year of report for being preserved on paper at any rate. The painting consists of a large bust of a female figure and remnants of two other male figures behind. The copy is exhibited with other paintings in the Archaeological Museum at Gwalior.

20. Hitherto, there was no clean and healthy drinking water near the caves. The water of the river below the caves which only survived in stagnant pools in the hot season, was used for drinking purposes, but it proved to be highly dangerous as being a very bad source of malaria and guinea-worm. Visitors, labourers and the supervising staff all

were exposed to and often actually suffered from this danger. Good drinking water in the close vicinity of the caves was therefore a long felt want. This was supplied this year by sinking a well near the caves at a safe distance from the river. The digging operation is well nigh over and the construction of the retaining walls will be taken up as soon as possible.

21. A piece of metalled road connecting the caves with the Sardarpur-Kukshi road is being constructed under the supervision of the P. W. D. This will greatly conduce to the convenience of visitors, especially of those who use cars.

22. *Udaygiri* (District Bhilsa).—This group of caves was cleared of debris and partially conserved years before. The only work done here this year was that a signboard engraved on stone giving a brief account of the caves for the information of visitors, was put up.

23. *Narwar Fort*.—Monuments on the fort which have already been conserved, necessitated some more repairs consequent on the damage caused by the rain. Thus, portions of the compound walls of the Catholic church which had collapsed were rebuilt. The tops of the walls were made water-tight by putting coping stones to avoid further damage. The roof slabs on the church hall were relieved of a thick layer of old roof consisting of earth and decayed lime which instead of serving as a protection only helped the decay of the stone slabs by absorbing rain water and acting as a superfluous heavy weight. Similarly patches of ruined masonry and coping were renewed in Sikandar Lodi's mosque and the *dargah* of Madar Shah.

24. *Surwaya* (District Narwar).—The monuments at Surwaya were conserved in Samvat 1973 (Year 1916-17). One of these monuments, namely the 'Hindu monastery' carried a two storeyed later structure upon its western wing. This structure was totally uninteresting being made up of ordinary plain small rubble masonry, and it presented an ugly contrast to the large cut stone masonry of the original building. Moreover it seriously blocked the view of the original monument. At the time of initial conservation this later structure was suffered to remain with a view to interfere as little as possible with the existing condition of the monument. In order to remove this standing eye-sore and to expose the imposing monastic building to full view even from the entrance, the ugly accretion was dismantled and cleared away.

25. A few ceiling slabs of the original building which were left hanging after the removal of the later structure were put into a safe condition. Part of the original pavement which had been upset was reset properly. Iron rails put up as supports for cracked beams and slabs during the initial conservation were painted to prevent oxidation. Descriptive signboards were provided at the inner entrance gate. The wooden gate at the outer entrance was in a dilapidated condition. It was replaced by an iron gate. The enclosure walls were damaged in places. They were restored and covered with coping stones. The well inside the monastery was freed from silt.

26. *Gwalior*.—The south-west column of the southern verandah of the tomb of Mohammad Ghaus bears a Persian inscription. The *jali* railing which is said to have been set up in Mr. Lake's time abuts against the inscription and has thus concealed a part of it. No photograph or impression of the inscription had been taken so far. To supply this want, part of the railing touching the inscribed column was temporarily removed and was reset after the photograph and impression had been taken. The tops of a few tombs in the yard were paved with stone slabs. A warning notice board was set up.

27. Some additions were done to the Gujari Mahal in the Fort in which the Archæological Museum is housed. The room which was fitted last year for the exhibition of Bagh paintings was found not to have sufficient light for the proper illumination of the paintings. Hence sky-lights were opened out in the roof. A water installation consisting of a masonry cistern connected to the well with pipe was provided as the existing menial staff could not otherwise cope with the requirements of water for the maintenance of the flower pot garden in the Museum.

28. An iron sheet signboard put up in front of the outer gate of the Gujari Mahal calling attention of visitors to the Archæological Museum, was replaced with one engraved on a stone slab, the latter being more lasting, as also more decent.

29. Another signboard on stone was set up outside the Gwalior gate of the Fort, giving information about the visiting hours of the Museum and also advising such visitors as proposed to see the Fort on elephant back to mount the elephant after seeing the Museum. This notice is intended to save disappointment or unnecessary expenses and trouble to visitors.

30. *Antri* (District Gird).—It is well known to the students of history that Abul Fazl, the favourite *Vasir* of Akbar and the learned author of the *Ain-i-Akbari* and *Akbarnama*, was murdered at the instigation of Prince Salim (afterwards Emperor Jahangir) at or in the vicinity of Antri, a large village some 16 miles to the south of Gwalior on the old road leading from Delhi to the Deccan. A small modern room on a raised platform on the northern outskirts of the town shelters a tomb which is believed locally to be the tomb of Abul Fazl. There is no authentic record in the form of an inscription or otherwise to corroborate the above belief. Moreover the tiny structure is too poor a monument to the memory of so great a man. This however looks not at all strange when the circumstances which attended and followed the demise of the talented victim are taken into consideration. The tomb was conserved this year under instructions from higher authorities.

31. The structure of the monument was already in a fair state of preservation. All that was needed was to open out and tidy up the place and to make the monument better known. To achieve this end, the following items were done. In front of and close to the only door to the shrine on its west there was a compound wall leaving very little open space. The

wall was therefore dismantled and rebuilt at a distance of about 14 feet further west to provide enough open space in front of entrance. The one door to the shrine was just on the opposite side of the cart track which passes by the tomb. The passer-by therefore carried an impression that the room had no entrance door at all. To do away with this wrong impression another door was pierced in the east wall of the shrine room looking towards the road and a flight of steps was provided on this side of the platform. The old wooden door flaps which had become decayed were renewed. Petty repairs were done to the retaining wall of the platform. A few drains were provided in the parapet wall of the platform to carry away rain water from the top of the platform. Two inscription boards in Hindi and English giving a brief history of the tomb were stuck up in the walls of the shrine room to enlighten visitors. The surrounding ground was levelled, cleared and tidied up and boundary stones were fixed up. A notice board warning the public in general and the inhabitants in the neighbourhood in particular against damaging the monument or making the surroundings dirty was set up. A signboard calling attention to the monument was put up at the junction where the approach road to Antri branches off from the Agra-Bombay Road.

32. *Lashkar*.—Another monument, similar in nature to the tomb of Abul Fazl, was taken up for conservation this year under similar circumstances. It is an open *chhatra* of the gallant Rani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi who fell fighting in a battle in 1858 near Gangadas-ki-Shala at Gwalior. But as the necessary procedure for the acquisition of the land could not be completed in the year of report the actual work of conservation had to be postponed till the next year.

33. *Kadwaha* (District Esagarh).—The village of Kadwaha which is referred to under the name 'Kadambagaha' in a 10th century inscription on the Khokhai monastery at Ranod (District Narwar) appears to have been an important centre of religious worship. In addition to a large Hindu monastery which was in later times enclosed in a *gadhi* (fortress), this village possesses clustered round it more than a dozen temples, which perhaps entitles the place to be called the 'Khajraha' of the Gwalior State. The temples some of which are Vaishnava and the rest Saiva are fair specimens of mediæval temples though many of them are small and now partly in a ruined condition. These monuments were listed more than ten years ago. They were thoroughly examined from the conservation point of view in the year of report, and conservation notes and estimates of repairs were drawn up.

34. *Miscellaneous Places*.—Similar notes and estimates were prepared with regard to the temples and monastery at Terahi, the temples at Mahua (District Narwar) and some minor monuments at Chanderi (District Esagarh) which still await repairs. A conservation note was also drawn up on the Shahajahani mosque at Gwalior. This mosque originally a fine structure is now in a very advanced state of ruins. The surviving portion which consists merely of a back wall, two side walls and a plat-

form in front of the mosque is still well worth conservation. These projects will go to make up further programme of conservation works after the works already in hand have been completed.

VI. Annual Upkeep.

35. Annual clearance and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of monuments already conserved.

VII. Exploration.

(a) Excavations.

36. No excavations were undertaken in the year of report. The excavations at Pawaya are left incomplete for want of funds. Ujjain, Besnagar and other sites are also awaiting investigation. But the difficulty of getting funds appears to be insuperable at any rate till the conservation of known monuments has been well nigh completed.

(b) Listing of Monuments.

37. Thirty-five monuments situated at eleven different places comprising ruins of mediæval temples, sculptures, *sati* and memorial pillars, with and without inscriptions were added to the list during the year of report. Appendix C shows a list of these monuments. They may be described briefly as under :—

38. *Bhilsa*.—In an open square in front of the Gandhi gate of the old city wall stands a dwarf stone pillar with a wedge-shaped top and looking like a guard stone as it touches the edge of the adjoining road. The portion of the pillar above ground measures 2' 3" high, 1' 2" broad, and 7" thick. The pillar is of interest owing to a Persian record incised on it in a sunken panel. The inscription is dealt with under Epigraphy below.

39. *Kulwar* (District Esagarh).—The Esagarh-Chanderi road passes by the ruins of a few old sculptures and *sati* stones near village Kulwar about 4 miles south of Esagarh. Under a Pipal tree near the western edge of the road are lying scattered a few sculptures among which are two or three images of Vishnu, an equal number of Siva-lingas, an image of Ganesa and one of a Nagadeva (serpent god). There are also a few broken *sati* pillars.

40. One of these *sati* pillars is still standing. It has four sculptured panels one above another. The uppermost panel depicts that a man and two women are worshipping a Siva linga. The panel next below and the lowest one each shows a fight between two horsemen. The intermediate panel that is the third from the top-most contains a man lying on a couch with his feet being shampooed by a woman.

41. Below the sculptured portion of the pillar is an inscription in degenerate Sanskrit dated in V. S. 329 (which is to be read 1329, the first digit having been damaged). Some letters of the inscription have been obliterated. But so far as the legible portion goes it seems to show that the pillar is the memorial of Kavalayadevi and Kuntadevi, two wives

of a Kachhavaha Rajput prince named Sihadeva who is styled Maharajadhiraja. The inscription also records that the pillar was made by Devapaladeva, brother of the deceased. The beginning and the end of the inscription are badly damaged.

42. *Anghora* (District Esagarh).—This is a small hamlet $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles south of Kadwaha. A furlong to the south-west of the hamlet is a shrine with a porch reconstructed with the materials of an 11th century temple. On the lintel of the doorway Siva and Parvati are sculptured in the centre, Vishnu and Lakshmi on the northern end, and Brahma and Brahmani on the southern end. In the exterior decoration of the walls are seen the sculptures of the guardians of the quarters (*dikpalas*), goddesses, Surya and Ganesa. A modern sculpture of a goddess is now enshrined in the temple but the original temple was possibly dedicated to goddess Mahishamardini whose mutilated sculpture is lying outside the temple. On a floor slab at the back of the shrine is a pilgrim's record dated V. S 1157.

43. Close by in a big hut a mutilated sculpture of Hanuman is lying on the ground in three pieces. Judging from the plan, the temple consisted of a shrine and a porch. What survives of it at present is the pillars which are standing and supporting the architraves and ceiling slabs. The carving and design of pillars resembles that of the *Solakhambi* hall at Badoh (District Bhilsa) which indicate that the temple was as old as the 8th or 9th century A. C. Two or three sculptures of the goddess Mahishamardini which are lying close by may have pertained to this temple.

44. *Sakarva* (District Esagarh).—This is a small village two miles west of Kadwaha and is located on the south-west slope of a hill now utilised for quarrying purposes. The village is an old one as it possesses an old tank and a number of ruined temples and memorial pillars ranging in date from the 11th to the 15th century A. C.

45. The tank which lies to the west of the hamlet is bounded on the north and the east by a strong dam about 50' wide made up of earthwork lined on both faces with big blocks of stone and having bathing *ghats* at intervals. The tank has been repaired and slightly extended in recent times for the purposes of irrigation. But it evidently dates from the 11th century A. C. to which period belong also the temples the ruins of which stand on the western and the northern banks of the tank.

46. There are four temples, two on the western and two on the northern bank.

47. The southern temple of the western group faces to the west and has a shrine room having a pillared hall of three bays in front. The shrine is 9'9" $\times$ 8' and the hall is 18' long east to west and 8' broad north to south. No *sikhara* is preserved. On the dedicatory or the central block of the door lintel is carved the figure of Ganesa. On the exterior of the temple, the niche in the north side wall shelters an image of Brahma,

that in the east or back wall, a figure of Ganesa, and the one in the south side wall a sculpture of Surya. The shrine room contains an idol of Mahishamardini and also one of a Jaina Tirthamkara leaning against a side wall. There is another Jaina figure outside against the south side wall.

48. The other temple in this group which is just close to the temple described above, also faces to the west and is a shrine with a porch, the whole measuring 11' x 9' externally. The shrine room carries a pyramidal roof like the temple known as Chandalamadh which is not far from this place (in the limits of the village of Kadwaha). The exterior niches of this temple contain the images of Surya on the east, Ganesa on the south and Vishnu on the north. At the back of this group of temples is a *sati* memorial half buried in the ground. The height of the portion of the pillar above ground is 4'3", the width and the thickness being 1'5" and 9" respectively. There are on this pillar three panels of sculpture one above another as usual. The lowest panel contains a fight between two foot-soldiers with sword and shield in hand. The middle panel shows a couple worshipping a Siva-linga. The top panel shelters a bust of a man with folded hands flanked on each side by a female. The pillar bears no inscription (the base underground was exposed and examined) but judging from the sculpture it may be assigned to the 10th or 11th Century A. C.

49. The other memorial pillar, equally old, which is situated on the north bank of the tank is interesting for the rather unusual subjects sculptured on it. The dressed portion above ground of this pillar is 4'3" high, 1'6" wide and 7½" thick. It has likewise three panels of sculptures. In the lowest are pictured a mother with a baby in lap and a man standing by. In the middle panel is a seated four-armed god flanked with a kneeling devotee (a male and a female) on either side. The top panel shelters a human bust with only two hands carrying a citron and a rosary. There is no inscription on this pillar either.

50. The northern group of temples at Sakarra referred to above also consists of two temples. Both the temples are shrines with porches in front but now without *sitharas*. Both temples measure 18' x 11'3" on the outside, both have door frames devoid of any sculpture, and both are empty. One of them faces to the east and the other to exactly the opposite direction. The niches on the exterior of the former bear the sculptures of the goddesses Varahi on the south, Vaishnavi on the west and Parvati on the north. The latter temple has its niches occupied by the sculptures of Parvati (north wall) Ardhanarisvara (east wall) and Brahma (south wall).

51. But above anything else the village Sakarra abounds in *sati* and memorial pillars. There is regularly a crop of such pillars standing round a hut on the top of a hillock nearly a quarter of a mile to the east of the village. Besides, there are some stray pillars also, both on the east and north-east of the village. The total number of these may come up to twenty or more. Most of them bear dated inscriptions some of which refer to contemporary Muhammadan Rulers. One of them refers to the Chief

Ramadeva and another to Muhammad (Tughlaq ?). The dates range from V. S. 1281 to 1501. Some of the pillars are memorials of *satis* and others of warriors who laid down their lives in a battle. Curiously three of such pillars are dated on the same day, namely, the 8th day of the dark fortnight of the month Sravana V. S. 1304. It is probable that all these persons lost their lives in one and the same fight. The sculptured panels on the pillars bear the familiar scenes of fight, the warriors' devotions and enjoyments in heaven after death. The rows of cows in some of these memorials further show that the skirmishes were fought over the kidnapping of these sacred animals.

52. *Dinara*. (District Narwar).—Dinara, sixteen miles west of Jhansi on the Jhansi-Shivpuri road, is known for the large *Tal* or tank said to have been built by Raja Birsingh Deo of Orchha, a contemporary of Akbar and Jahangir, though no inscriptional evidence to this effect exists on the monument. Three inscriptions slovenly inscribed on slabs—two in the floors of two *Surais* and one on a coping stone in the top-most line of the *ghat* of the tank—are merely casual records.

53. The tank is of an irregular shape and is said to be sixteen miles in circuit when full. On the west and south it is bounded by a chain of small hills and on the north and the east by a strong dam consisting of earthwork lined with heavy block of stone and boulders on the inner face. On the west bank of the tank where there is a band in the chain of hills is a well-built stone *ghat* known as Surai ghat from *Surais* or small kiosques which is a decorative feature of the *ghat*. The *ghat* is built in three stages. Each stage has a number of cross stairs. There are *Surais* on the top-most stage of the *ghat*. The middle stage has no *Surai* although there are projecting brackets which were possibly intended to carry such *Surais*. In the lowest stage there is only one *Surai* in the centre. In the uppermost stage is a pillared hall and a long narrow cell just below it in the middle stage.

54. The *ghat* is strongly built with large stones and slabs made for the purpose although there are some stones both plain dressed as well as carved which evidently have been taken from the ruins of older temples and monasteries.

55. Unfortunately this fine *ghat* is now in a neglected condition. It shows some growth of shrubs and vegetation in the masonry joints which is bound to prove destructive to it in future. The *ghat* is itself used by the villagers for unclean purposes. It will be well if the Irrigation Department who use the tank for purposes of irrigation would take proper care of this old *ghat* and look to its upkeep and cleanliness.

56. Birsingh Deo has also built a *garhi* on a hillock adjoining the *ghat* and overlooking the tank, but this uninteresting structure is now in a dilapidated condition.

57. Beyond the *ghat*, in the western portion of the dam between two hillocks, water leaking has formed a small stream. In the ground flooded

by this stream, stands a grove of *Ketaki* trees now in a decaying condition for want of care though it seems to have been once a rich garden. Beyond it is what is called *Kela Bag* or a plantain grove again, once a flourishing garden but now in a desolate condition.

58. *Kaildhar* (District Narwar).—It is a small hamlet on the bank of a hilly *nala* situated about five miles to the west of Lukwasa, a village twenty-three miles south of Shivpuri on the Agra-Bombay Road. The village tradition points to a place on the left bank of the *nala* as the seat of the sage Kapila. This place has a crude cavity in the bank formed by heaping of boulders and some carved debris of older temples and topped by a small modern *chhatri*. Below the cavity is a platform built later on. A *gomukh* is built inside the cavity from which water is said to flow and a jet of milk is said to gush out from it once a year. It was dry at the time of inspection. The jet emerging from the *gomukh* was known as Kailasa-dhara which now survives in the name Kaildhar. This is how the local people explain the name of the place. Close by is another reservoir of living water of modern build in which are also stuck up some old carved sculptures and debris. Both this reservoir and *nala* are held sacred and are used for depositing the ashes of the dead in the surrounding locality.

59. The only thing of Archæological interest here consists in the remnants of two 10th century shrines. *Sikharas* of the both have disappeared, and being built on a slope of the bank of the *nala* the temples are half buried in the earth slipping from the bank above. One of the temples has lost most of its body and is preserved only up to a little above the plinth. The other temple has survived up to a little above the door frame. The plinth of the latter is buried and the porch disappeared. The interior is divided into two apartments by pilasters. The back portion shelters a Siva-linga and has a lotus flower carved on the ceiling. The ceiling slab of the front apartment is plain. The door frame is preserved on which the outer line of decoration is a scroll and the middle one has panels inset with pairs of lovers. The lintel has a standing female on each end, while in the centre is a female *kichaka* with arms raised up to hold a sort of crown. Both the temples have a double course of sculptures among which may be seen Lakulisa, Kaumari, Yama and a dwarf dressed like a soldier and seated on a rhinoceros. Another, a female goddess, has a god and a lion in the corner and a chameleon or crocodile—like the figure below its feet. She has a book of the scriptures in one hand and a ladle in another.

60. Near the temples and scattered in vicinity are a few fragments of sculptures. Only one of these which deserves notice is a standing male image carrying a bowl on its head. The outer edge of the bowl has lotus petals carved on it. Close to it a female is standing looking back. Both are stuck up in the retaining wall of the reservoir. There is a number of *chhatris* of modern times belonging to *gusains* who once lived in the village, but they are too uninteresting and poor to deserve notice. The monuments at Kaildhar were visited by the Inspector. This note is the result of that visit.

61. *Karera* (District Narwar).—A fortified town situated on the bank of the Mahuwar river known as Madhumati in old inscriptions and books, is thirty miles by metalled road either from Jhansi or Shivpuri. The chief monument to be seen here is the picturesque fort which is perched on a peak of sandstone some 200 feet high, immediately to the east of the town. It is said to have been built by the Bundela Rajas of Orchha and is now quite uncared for and overgrown with rank jungle or useless shrubs. The buildings inside, mostly residential, are now mere dilapidated ghostly walls. There are two or three small tanks which are said to have natural springs, though at the time of inspection they contained only some dirty water. A modern Siva temple, popularly known as Tembakesvara which is evidently a corruption of Triambakesvara, shelters a large *linga*. The basin or *jaladhari* is four and half feet in diameter and about two feet high. The *linga* which is also about two feet in height is one and a half feet in diameter. Further to the east of Triambakesvara temple is a *dargah* and a mosque. On the central *mehrab* of the mosque is a Persian inscription recording that the mosque was built by Salar Khan during the reign of Shahjahan II. The date which was given below is now lost owing to the peeling of the letters. The tomb or *dargah* which is close by is evidently of the builder of the mosque. The fort has two approach roads with gates, the principal one being on the north-west, through the town. Flanking this road, but outside the gate, is a three-storeyed building known as Kacheri which seems never to have reached completion. The gates as well as other buildings noticed above are of no historical or architectural value. So there is practically nothing of archæological interest about this fort.

62. On the south of the fort is another small peak, in a crevice of which is worshipped a Siva-*linga* known as Guptesvara. Adjoining to it are built a few rooms for *sadhus* to live in and steps are provided to reach these. There is, however, nothing of special interest about this place except a stone, at the top of the peak, of metallic composition and detached from the mother rock, which when struck rings like a bell.

63. *Terahi* (District Narwar).—This is a village six miles to the north-east of Kadwaha mentioned in para No. 33 above. It was visited twice before and its antiquities listed. During this year's inspection visit, one more monument came to light. This is an interesting memorial pillar with all the four faces carved. The stone is lying two furlongs south-west of Terahi on the way to the river Mahuwar (Madhumati) near the large image of Ganesa, and is about 4' 6" high and about 1' 3" broad on each face. There are four courses of sculptures one above another. The lowest and the second course each consists of riders on horse back. The third course represents worship of Siva-*linga*, and the top consists of a big Siva-*linga* with busts on all four faces. The lowest and the top courses are four faced while at the second course the column is round.

64. *Sujwaja* (District Gird).—It is a small village about a mile and a half south-west of Tighra, which is eleven miles by *pucca* road to

the west of Lashkar where there is the biggest modern irrigation tank in Gwalior State. Near the village Malipura, but in the limits of the village Sujwaya, are the ruins of some Jaina temples in two groups. The temples have almost been razed to the ground and even their plans are not clearly seen. Heaps of carved debris, ceiling slabs and stray mutilated sculptures of *Tirthankaras* are all what can be seen at site. The remains belong approximately to the 11th century A. C. These ruins were visited and the note drawn up by the Inspector.

65. *Hasalpur* (District Sheopur).—This village was visited for a second time this year. In addition to the monuments listed in the past, a few monuments attracted my notice during this visit, namely:—

(a) An inscribed *sati* pillar standing outside the village flanking the cart track from the village to Khojipura station.

(b) An inscribed stone post said to be found recently in the *kot* or village fortifications and now planted near the temple of Rama in the centre of the village.

(c) Another inscribed slab stuck up near the post mentioned above.

66. Another object of interest near this village is a *sati* monument hardly a hundred years old. It stands on the north-west outskirts of the village at a little distance from the river. The peculiarity of this monument is that besides being sheltered in a *chhatri* or kiosque, the design of the *sati* post itself is rather unusual. Here the deceased couple is inset in a niche carved on the front face of the post and a half opened lotus flower is carved on its back face. An inscribed stone pillar planted near the approach steps of the *chhatri* gives the history of the *sati*.

VIII. Epigraphy.

67. One hundred and fifteen Hindu and sixteen Muslim, or 131 inscriptions in all were copied or noticed in 15 different places during the year of report. These severally belong to Besnagar and Bhilsa (District Bhilsa), Chanderi, Naderi, Kadwaha and Sakarra (District Esagarh), Gwalior Fort and Antri (District Gird), Bhatnawar, Dinara, Karera and Narwar (District Narwar), Hasalpur and Rameshwar (District Sheopur).

68. Out of these, 29 Hindu and 16 Muslim inscriptions are new discoveries while the rest were known already and were only copied for office record in the year of report. A detailed analysis of inscriptions will be found in Appendix D.

69. There are only two records of historical importance among the newly discovered Sanskrit inscriptions.

70. One of these was engraved on the lintels of a porch of a temple. (Compare the inscription on the lintels of the porch of the Chaturbhuj temple on Gwalior Fort.) Only two out of the four pieces of our inscription have been recovered from a modern pavement in the Gwalior Fort. The remaining portion of the inscription is not available yet and hence the object of the record is not quite clear. The

invocation at the beginning of the epigraph is addressed to God Visakha (Kartikeya). From this it may be inferred that the inscription was intended to record the construction of or a grant to, a temple of Visakha. The inscription mentions the names of Ramadeva (a Pratihara king of Kanauj) and his Brahmana official Vailla Bhatta who are also alluded to in the inscriptions on the Chaturbhuj temple on Gwalior Fort. The recovered portion of the inscription contains no date. But on palæographical grounds and from the mention of the two contemporary personages whose dates are already known, the inscriptions may be referred to the latter half of the 9th century A. C.

71. The other inscription was found on an old well about a mile to the east of Narwar town. It records the construction of the well by Asaditya, a Mathura Kayastha, in the reign of king Gopala of Narwar in V. S. 1338.

72. Among the remaining newly discovered inscriptions are the short records on the pedestals of rock-cut Jaina sculptures on Gwalior Fort which refer to the Tomara kings Dungara Sinha and his son Kirtti Sinha, the pilgrims' records on the temples at Kadwaha and the records on *sati* and memorial pillars at Sakarra and Kulwar.

73. The earliest of the Muslim inscriptions, dated in A. H. 893, is carved on the tomb of a merchant at Bhilsa and refers to the reign of Muhammad Shah Khilji I, Sultan of Malwa. The rest of the inscriptions refer to Humayun, Akbar, Shahjahan, Aurangzeb and Shah Alam, Mughal Emperors of Delhi, and all except two record the construction of mosques. One of the two exceptions is a sort of pilgrims' record on a pillar of the Tomb of Muhammad Ghaus, by one Muhammad Masum, a celebrated calligraphist of Akbar's court. The other (on a stone post at Bhilsa) mentions no king or date, but is interesting as it contains a royal warrant prohibiting the exaction of *begar* or forced labour from Kolis (Hindu weavers), and according to a local tradition, is ascribed to Aurangzeb or Alamgir.

74. The following Muslim inscriptions were published :—

- (1) The inscription on the entrance of the Bina-nim-ki-masjid, Ujjain. (*Indian Antiquary*, Vol. LVI., August 1927.)
- (2) The loose inscription from the dismantled Mochiwada Gate, now preserved in Madhava College, Ujjain. (*Indian Antiquary*, Vol. LVI., August 1927.)
- (3) The inscription on the Mughal mosque at Udaypur. (*Indian Historical Quarterly*, Vol. III., No. 4.)

IX. Numismatics.

75. Nineteen gold, 37 silver, 18,670 copper, 522 billon or 19,248 coins in all were examined during the year of report. (See Appendix E.)

76. The coins were received from the following sources:—

- (a) Out of the 19 gold coins, 13 were offered by a coin dealer for sale, while 6 were re-examined for selection for the Archaeological Museum from the duplicates in the collection of the State Museum which had been examined last year.

(b) Two lots of 20 and 4 respectively of silver coins were received from coin dealers, while 13 came from the duplicates in the collection of the State Museum.

(c) Out of the 18,670 copper coins, 2 coins were received in exchange from the Historical Society, Chhattisgarh. Two lots of 5 and 4 pieces were received for sale from dealers. The rest 18,659 were received as treasure-trove from the village Kotwal (ancient Kantipuri or Kuntalpur, one of the capitals of Nagas in the Tonwarghar District).

(d) The billon coins also came from a treasure-trove find at Bhat Pachlana, a village in the Ujjain District.

77. The coins examined range in date from B. C. 300 to A. C. 1800, represent some 14 different dynasties, and may be roughly classified as under:—

(1) Indo-Greeks (B. C. 300 to A. C. 100)—Alexander the Great, Diodotos, Euthydemos, Euthydemos with Agathokles, Eukratides, Heliokles, Antialkidas, Apollodotos, Menander and Hermaios.

(2) Indo-Parthian or Sakas (B. C. 115 to A. C. 100) — Vonones with Spalahora, Spalahora with Spalagadama, Azes II, Soter Megas.

(3) Indo-Scythians or Kushan (A. C. 70 to 200) — Kadphises II, Huvishka and Vasudeva.

(4) Guptas (A. C. 335 to 480)—Chandragupta II.

(5) Nagas (4th century A.C.)—'Kha' and 'Va' Naga, Bhima Naga, Skanda Naga, Brihaspati Naga, Ganapati Naga, Deva Naga and Purn Naga.

(6) Indo-Sessanian (A. C. 600 to 900)—Dramma pieces and a new type of coins not figured in any of the Coin Catalogues so far.

(7) Chandelas of Bundelkhand (11th century A. C.)—Kirtivarman Deva and Sallakshanavarman Deva.

(8) Kashmir (11th century A. C.)—king Anant and queen Didda.

(9) Haihayas of Maha Kosala or Eastern Chedi (Chhattisgarh) (A. C. 1140-1200)—Srimat Prithvi Deva and Pratapa Malla Deva.

(10) Second dynasty of Vijayanagar (16th century A. C.)—Krishnaraya

(11) Gurkhal dynasty of Nepal (18th century A. C.)—Prithvi Vikrama, Surendra Vikrama and Rajendra Vikrama.

(12) Suri dynasty of Delhi (A. C. 1540-1555)—Shershah.

(13) Mughal Emperors of Delhi (A. C. 1526-1858)—Akbar, Jahangir and Shahjahan, representing Ahmedabad and Surat mints.

(14) Nawabs of Oudh (A. C. 1800-1858)—Muhammad Ali, Amjad Ali and Wajid Ali.

78. Both the treasure-trove finds referred to above contain a large number of coins. The Kotwal find is specially rich and has yielded coins of almost all the types of Naga coins known so far.

As the hoard is a very large one, it was not possible to examine it thoroughly in the year of report. Only a passing inspection was made. When re-examined, it may perhaps yield new names and types. The find of Bhata Pachlana has yielded a peculiar type of Indo-Sessianian coins, the exact parallel of which has not so far been traced, though they have some resemblance to coins referred to in *C. M. I.* Plate VI. 20.

79. Out of the coins thus examined, 11 gold, 23 silver, 36 copper and 8 billon, or 78 coins in all were added to the Museum collection.

80. Out of these, 5 gold, 10 silver and 8 copper pieces were purchased from dealers. 2 copper coins were received in exchange as noted above, 6 gold and 13 silver coins came from duplicates of the State Museum. The remaining 26 copper and 8 billon coins were selected from the two treasure-trove finds referred to already.

X. Museum.

81. Seventeen stone images, 13 stone heads and limbs, 3 stone inscriptions, 2 stone capitals, an impression of a Persian inscription, 7 old miniature paintings in colour, and 11 gold, 23 silver, 36 copper and 8 mixed metal coins, or 121 antiquities in all were added to the Museum during the year of report and are set forth in Appendix F.

82. Out of these, stone sculptures came from Subania, Pawaya, Mamon and Naderi. One of the inscriptions has been removed from Surwaya fort where it lay so far, while two were recently discovered, built up in a modern pavement on Gwalior Fort, and acquired for the Museum. The impression was copied from a Persian inscription engraved on a corner pillar of the Mausoleum of Muhammad Ghaus not noticed anywhere so far.

83. Six of the seven miniature old paintings were purchased and one was received through the Private Secretary to H. H. the Maharaja Scindia. It was displayed so far in Baijabai's *chhatri* at Ujjain but was not in a proper setting.

84. Out of the 78 coins, 5 gold, 10 silver and 8 copper coins were purchased from dealers, while the remaining came from treasure-trove found in the State, or were received in exchange, as detailed under Numismatics.

85. In the year of report, 145 European and 415 Indian visitors recorded their names in the Visit Book kept at the Archæological Museum, Gwalior, though, according to the Curator's report, many more actually visited the institution. The visitors represent almost all the cultured nations in the world, the chief among them being U. S. A., England, Germany, South Africa, Newzealand and Australia. Most of the visitors have recorded their appreciation of the way in which the Museum is being maintained.

86. The names of the following distinguished visitors to the Museum deserve mention:—

Their Excellencies Sir G. Goschen Governor, of Madras, and Lady Goschen, Lt.-Col. C. G. Crosthwaite and Col. Heale, the past and present Residents at Gwalior, Mrs. Heale, Dr. M. Sciller, Court Physician to His

Majesty the King of Afghanistan, H. Von Glasenapp, Professor of Sanskrit, Berlin University, Professor H. Luders, the well-known German Indologist, and Mrs. Luders, Members of the Butler Committee, Sir George and Lady Godfrey, Mr. Robinson, Guardian to H. H. Maharaja Scindia, and Mrs. Robinson, the delegates of the Marathi Sahitya Sammelana of whom the chief were the President Mr. Ane, M. L. A., of Yeotmal, Rao Bahadur C. V. Vaidya of Poona, Sardar and Lady Kibe of Indore, Professor Potdar of the Bharata Itihasa Samsodhaka Mandala of Poona, Mr. Yadava Rao Kale, ex-President of the C. P. Council, Mr. Wajhe, the well-known scholar of Silpa Sastra, K. N. Dikshit, Superintendent, Archaeological Survey of India, Eastern Circle, Calcutta, and H. H. Swami Gyananand and Swami Dayanand of the Bharata Dharma Mahamandala.

87. Another interesting item to be reported this year is that the Museum premises with its exhibits was the scene of operation of one of the leading Cinema Companies of Germany who exposed many films under special orders of the Council of Regency.

XI. Miscellaneous.

88. (i) *At-Home*.—As remarked in the Annual Administration Report of Samvat 1983, it was decided to hold the At-Home every three years. But as the All-India Marathi Sahitya Sammelana was attended by a large number of delegates from all parts of India, most of whom were interested in Archaeology, a Departmental At-Home was specially arranged to meet all delegates of the above Sammelana and the Members of the Council of Regency, Officials and the gentry of the State. The most interesting feature of this At-Home was a lantern lecture on the sensational discoveries of the Mohenjo-daro and Harrappa excavations delivered by Mr. K. N. Dikshit, M.A., Superintendent, Archaeological Survey of India, Eastern Circle, Calcutta.

89. (ii) *Distinguished visitors to the monuments*.—Two important groups of Archaeological monuments, *viz.*, that of Surwaya near Shivpuri, the summer capital of the State, and of the Bagh Caves (District Amjhera), are gaining steadily in popularity and attracting visitors.

90. According to names recorded in the Visitors' Book kept at the Surwaya monuments, 16 European and 61 Indians visited the monuments. The following are some of the distinguished visitors to Surwaya:—H. H. the Maharaja Gaikwar of Baroda and party, Rao Bahadur C. V. Vaidya, Sahibzada Aftab Ahmad Khan of Aligarh, Sardar Sir Sultan Ahmad Khan Sahib, Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar and Captain Bapu Rao Sahib Pawar, Members of the Council of Regency, Administrative Officer, Irrigation Department, and Administrative Officer, P.W.D., the Director, Land Records, the Settlement Commissioner, and all the Subas (District Collectors) of the State. The European visitors were mostly Military Officers.

91. Similarly the Bagh Caves were visited by a good number of visitors of whom 17 only have recorded their signatures. 10 of these are Europeans

and the rest were officials of our State and of the adjoining States of Indore, Dhar and Bori, and Syed Fyzee Rahaman the well-known artist of Bombay, who was specially invited by our Government to examine the old wall-paintings on the caves and to suggest measures for their preservation.

92. The European visitors included Rev. A. V. Gaitwal, Dr. F. H. Rusick and party, Miss D. D. Harvey and Mrs. Robinson, Mrs. La Laze, Dr. and Mrs. R. A. King, Mr. and Mrs. N. R. Lynch Blasse, I. C. S. The Agent to the Governor-General in Central India also intended to visit the caves but had to cancel his visit at the very eleventh hour owing to an unforeseen cause.

93. In view of the situation of these monuments in the deep of the country and away from Railway communication the progress of visitors is fairly encouraging.

94. (iii) *Superintendent's visits to monuments outside the State.*—One of the two places which I visited outside the State for purposes of exploration as noted in para No, 10 above was Devaguradia, a small hamlet at the foot of a hill of the same name about six miles to the south-east of Indore. Last year Mr. A. S. Bhandarkar of Indore wrote an article identifying Devaguradia with the Devagiri hill mentioned in the *Meghaduta* of Kalidasa. This article was sent to Sir John Marshall, Director-General of Archaeology in India, for approval before publication. Sir John Marshall, however, forwarded it to me for opinion, as it clashed with my identification of Devagiri with a hill called Deva-Dungri near Unhel in Gwalior State, a note on which had already appeared in the *Annual Report* of the Archaeological Survey of India for 1925-26.

95. I visited Devaguradia in company of Mr. Bhandarkar in order to verify on the spot the argument adduced by him in favour of his identification of Devaguradia with Devagiri. On visiting the place I found that the temples and other relics for which Mr. Bhandarkar claimed a high antiquity were mere modern buildings and that there was not the slightest justification on monumental or historical grounds for Mr. Bhandarkar's contention. In spite of my explanations Mr. Bhandarkar thought it fit to stick to his views and published a paper on the subject in the *Indian Antiquary*, Vol. LVII, P. P. 23-24. I, therefore, propose to write a detailed article setting forth my conclusions on the subject.

96. The other place which was visited was Nagari, situated about seven miles to the north of the famous fortress of Chitorgarh in Mewar. The modern village of Nagari marks the site of the ancient town Madhyamika. Professor D. R. Bhandarkar had carried out excavations at this place and exposed some interesting relics. From his report I found that some of the monuments discovered there were much like the monuments we had excavated at Sondni and Khilchipura near Mandsaur and at Pawaya, and I believed that a visit to and inspection of the actual antiquities at Nagari would help me in the better understanding and solution of some of the problems which encountered me during the excavations at Mandsaur and Pawaya. The visit had the desired effect.

Publications.

97. Three books were published in the year of report, viz, (1) *The Bagh Caves*, (2) *A Guide to the Archaeological Museum at Gwalior* and (3) *Gwalior Fort Album* (third edition). The first of these is a joint publication of the India Society and the Gwalior Archaeological Department. It has supplied a long-felt want and is greatly appreciated both in India and abroad. It has cost the Department a large amount of money, labour and care in preparing and collecting the material for the volume. It is only regretted that two great personages to whom the credit of this publication is largely due—namely, His Highness the late Maharaja Sir Madhav Rao Scindia and Col. C. E. Luard,—have unfortunately not lived to see the publication through. Extracts from a few of the press appreciations are given below.

98. *The London Times*.—But no Western paintings—though the affinity is here greater than that between European and Chinese art—can equal these in grandeur.

99. *The Daily Telegraph*.—What is certain is that as works of art they are beyond all praise.....; as decorative designs they are superb; their colour is something to remember; as expressions of life and movement they represent not only a curious and fascinating culture, or a particular moment in the evolution of art, but have a genuinely universal value.

100. *The Theosophist*.—The world of culture owes to these authorities a debt of gratitude for not only putting these art treasures within reach of all but what is more important, perpetuating these remnants of unsurpassed art for the future. For even in the last half century much of these, and other precious records, have vanished.

101. *The Hindu*.—But while the Ajanta frescoes are more religious in theme, depicting incidents from the previous lives of the Buddha with their human associations, the Bagh frescoes are more human depicting the life of the time with its religious associations. The exquisite austerity of Ajanta tends to obscure the personal element of the artist in the calm depiction of super personality. But in the Bagh frescoes the humanity of the theme gives free rein to the joy of the artist, though the general tone is of one gracious solemnity. The æsthetical element which is latent, almost cold in Ajanta is patent and pulsating in Bagh.

102. *The London Spectator*.—One after another, like stars in twilight, they take the eye, these points of dim radiance on the darkening sky of history moving the heart with a solemn joy and stirring the imagination to discovery until there stretches before the inner eye the re-created pageant of a vanished life.

103. *The Manchester Guardian*.—The remains of the paintings in these (Bagh) rock-hewn shrines are of far less extent than the Ajanta paintings, but rival or surpass them in beauty. What chiefly survives is a single composition representing a procession and festival. It is one of the most glorious paintings in the world. One is astounded by mastery of complex figure

design, by the beauty of relation between the forms, by the animation and grace of the movements and specially by the plastic sense so rare in Asiatic paintings. The mass and onward movement of the great elephants with their swaying riders are formidable; by contrast the group of girls encircling two male dancers is enchanting in its rhythm of supple forms, each exquisite in pose and gesture. The colouring is deep and ardent.

104. The second publication which was prepared in haste for the occasion of All-India Marathi Sahitya Sammelana is only a very brief *Guide to the Archæological Museum*. A fuller and more systematic *Guide* is yet to be brought out.

XIII. Photography and Drawing.

105. One hundred and three photographic negatives and 106 lantern slides were made during the year of report. Besides, a number of enlarged photographs of important monuments were prepared for exhibiting at certain stations on the G.I.P. Railway, in the Shivpuri Hotel and in carriages of G. L. Railway. Photographic prints were made and supplied to the orders of outside customers.

106. A copy in colours and another in outline were made of a newly found piece of fresco painting in cave No. 4 at Bagh.

107. Eleven Drawings were made during the year of report. For details see Appendices G, H and I.

XIV. Office Library.

108. One hundred and twenty two books and journals on history, art, architecture and allied subjects were added to the office library during the year of report. Of these ninety-seven were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and the Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due. The list of books is given in Appendix J.

XV. Income and Expenditure.

109. Statements of Income and Expenditure of the Department under different heads of budget during the year of report are set forth in Appendices K and L from which it will be seen that the annual expenditure was Rs. 40,088-13.10 including parts of the last year's special grants over and above the budget grant. The income from different sources is Rs. 166-4-8.

XVI. Concluding Remarks.

110. In conclusion I am deeply grateful to Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar Home Member, and Major Hashmat Ullah Khan Sahib, Member for Public Works, for the unfailing courtesy and valuable advice with which they continued to favour me in discharging the duties of my office. I am also deeply thankful to Sardar Sir Sultan Ahmad Khan Sahib for the keen interest he takes in the work of this Department.

M. B. Garde,
Superintendent of Archæology,
Gwalior State.

PART II.

APPENDICES.

APPENDIX A.

Tour-Diary of the Superintendent of Archæology,
for the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Year and month.	Date.	Movements and halts.
1927.		
July ...	1st-2nd	Gwalior to Ujjain. (thence on p. leave).
September	5th-6th	Gwalior to Simla.
	7th	Halt at Simla.
	7th-8th	Simla to Gwalior
November	8th	Gwalior to Antri and back.
	18th	Gwalior to Girdharpur
	19th	Girdharpur to Hasalpur <i>via</i> Khojeepera and back.
	20th	Girdharpur to Rameshvar and back.
	21st	Girdharpur to Gwalior.
	23rd	Gwalior to Satanwara.
	24th	Satanwara to Narwar.
	25th	Halt at Narwar.
	26th	Narwar to Shivpuri
	27th	Shivpuri to Surwaya.
	28th	Surwaya to Karera.
	29th	Karera to Dinara.
	30th	Dinara to Gwalior <i>via</i> Jhansi.
December	7th	Gwalior to Bhilsa.
	8th	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
	8th-9th	Bhilsa to Mhow <i>via</i> Ujjain.
	10th	Mhow to Bagh
	11th-13th	Halt at Bagh
	14th	Bagh to Bagh caves.
	15th-16th	Halt at Bagh caves.
December	17th	Caves to Bagh.
	18th	Bagh to Dhar.
	19th	Dhar to Mhow.
	"	Mhow to Ujjain.
	20th	Halt at Ujjain.
	21st	Ujjain to Indore.
	22nd	Indore to Devaguradia and back.
	23rd	Indore to Chitorgarh <i>via</i> Mandasaur.
	24th-25th	Availed holidays.
	26th	Chitorgarh to Nagari and back.
	26th-28th	Chitorgarh to Gwalior <i>via</i> Ujjain.
1928.		
January...	15th-16th	Gwalior to Mungaoli.
	16th	Mungaoli to Chanderi.
	17th-19th	Halt at Chanderi
	20th	Chanderi to Esagarh.
	21st	Esagarh to Kadwaha.
	22nd	Halt at Kadwaha.
	23rd	
	24th	Kadwaha to Anghora and back.
	25th	Kadwaha to Terahi and back.
	26th	Kadwaha to Akajheri <i>via</i> Sakarra and Ranod.

Year and month.	Date.	Movements and halts.
March ...	27th	Akajheri to Surwaya
	28th	Surwaya to Gwalior <i>via</i> Jhansi.
	1st-3rd	Gwalior to Mhow.
	3rd	Mhow to Bagh.
	4th-5th	Halt at Bagh.
	6th	Bagh to Mhow.
	7th-8th	Mhow to Gwalior (broke journey at Bhilsa for inspection of caves at Udaygiri).
April ...	19th	Gwalior to Antri and back.
April ...	24th	Gwalior to Surwaya <i>via</i> Shivpuri.
	25th	Surwaya to Shivpuri.
	26th	Shivpuri to Narwar.
	27th	Narwar to Satanwara.
	28th	Satanwara to Gwalior.
	29th	Gwalior to Morena.
May ...	30th	Morena to Suhania.
May ...	1st	Suhania to Morena.
	2nd	Morena to Gwalior.
June ...	10th	Gwalior to Bhopal.
	11th	Bhopal to Mhow.
	"	Mhow to Dhar.
	12th	Dhar to Bagh.
	13th-15th	Halt at Bagh.
	16th	Bagh to Mhow.
	"	Mhow to Ujjain.
	17th-18th	Ujjain to Gwalior.

Tour-Diary of the Offg. Superintendent.

1927		
July ...	30th	Gwalior to Antri.
	31st	Antri to Gwalior.
August ...	14th	Gwalior to Ujjain.
	15th	Ujjain to Mandasaur and Sondni.
	16th	Sondni to Mandasaur.
	"	Mandasaur to Ujjain.
	17th	Halt at Ujjain.
	18th	Ujjain to Gwalior.

APPENDIX B.

List of Monuments conserved during the year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Serial No.	Name of place.	Name of monument conserved.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		Total.	AMOUNT SPENT.		REMARKS.	
			Last year.			Last year.			
			Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.		Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.		
1	Bagh ...	Bagh Caves	...	17,676 8 0	17,676 8 0	...	14,939 2 6	Rs. a. p. 2 6	
2	Do.	Digging a well near the caves.	250 0 0	...	250 0 0	...	250 0 0	Rs. a. p. 0 0	
3	Gwalior ...	Tomb of Md. Ghaus...	83 0 0	...	83 0 0	...	79 12 3	Rs. a. p. 3 3	
4	Do.	Gujari Mahal ...	293 0 0	...	293 0 0	...	246 7 3	Rs. a. p. 3 3	
5	Do.	Museum Building ...	273 0 0	...	273 0 0	...	234 15 9	Rs. a. p. 9 9	
6	Do.	Notice for Museum on Fort gate.	113 0 0	...	113 0 0	...	111 13 6	Rs. a. p. 6 6	
7	Lashkar ...	Chhatri of Maharani of Jhansi	1,353 0 0	...	1,353 0 0	...	7 0 0	Rs. a. p. 0 0	
8	Antri ...	Tomb of Abul Fazl ...	515 0 0	...	515 0 0	...	497 8 11	Rs. a. p. 11 11	
9	Suhania ...	Kakanmadh Temple ...	...	106 0 6	106 0 6	...	106 0 6	Rs. a. p. 6 6	
10	Surwaya ...	Monuments in the fort,	991 0 0	...	991 0 0	...	724 3 6	Rs. a. p. 6 6	
11	Do.	Do.	59 0 0	...	59 0 0	...	29 12 9	Rs. a. p. 9 9	
12	Narwar ...	Do.	136 0 0	...	136 0 0	...	72 6 3	Rs. a. p. 3 3	
13	Do.	Do.	59 0 0	...	59 0 0	...	59 0 0	Rs. a. p. 0 0	
14	Badoh ...	Providing notice boards at monuments.	90 0 0	...	90 0 0	...	5 0 0	Rs. a. p. 0 0	
15	Udaygiri ...	Do.	325 0 0	...	325 0 0	...	321 2 3	Rs. a. p. 3 3	
Grand Total ...			4,540 0 0	17,782 8 6	22,322 8 6	...	2,639 2 5	15,045 3 0	Rs. a. p. 0 5 5
							17,684 5 5		

APPENDIX C.

Statement of Monuments listed or noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat, 1984.

No.	Place.	District.	Particulars.	Class.	REMARKS.
1	Bhilsa ...	Bhilsa.	A stone post with a Persian inscription in front of Gandhi Gate.	II.	
2	Anghora ...	Esagarh.	A ruined temple to the south-west of village.	III.	
3	"	"	Another ruined Siva temple 2 miles north-west of village in jungle.	III.	
4	Sakarra ...	"	Some inscribed <i>sati</i> memorial pillars round about the village.	II.	
5-6	"	"	Two ruined Hindu temples on the east bank of the tank.	II.	
7	"	"	A Jaina sculpture near the temple.	II.	
8-9	"	"	Two carved memorial pillars near the temples	II.	
10-11	"	"	Two more Hindu temples one facing east and the other west, on the northern bank of the tank.	II.	
12	Sujwaya ...	Gird.	Ruins of some Jaina temples of mediæval period with sculptures.	III.	
13	"	"	A pillar having a <i>chaumukha</i> as its capital near the above.	III.	
14	"	"	A finely carved Jaina <i>chaumukha</i> near the above.	III.	
15	"	"	Ruins of a Jaina temple with attendant shrines of mediæval period.	III.	
16	"	"	Ruins of two more Jaina temples in the vicinity.	III.	
17	Dinara ...	Narwar.	An old tank built by Raja Birsingh Deo of Orchha.	II.	
18	"	"	Surai ghat of the tank ...	II.	
19	"	"	<i>Gadhi</i> ...	III.	
20-21	Kaildhar ...	"	Two ruined Hindu temples to the east of village across a <i>nala</i> .	II.	
22	"	"	Fragments of sculptures built in a reservoir near above.	III.	
23	"	"	Fragments of sculptures heaped up on a platform, north of village.	III.	

No.	Place.	District.	Particulars.	Class.	REMARKS.
24	Karera ...	Narwar.	Fort.	III.	
25	"	"	A mosque with a Persian inscription ...	III.	
26	"	"	A modern temple with a large Siva-linga ...	III.	
27	"	"	A modern building called Kachehri ...	III.	
28	"	"	Guptesvar temple with a ringing ledge of rock near it.	III.	
29	Terahi ...	"	A carved memorial pillar south-west of village	II.	
30	Hasalpur ...	Sheopur.	Fragments of sculptures of the mediæval period in the walls of a modern temple.	I.	
31	"	"	An inscribed <i>sati</i> stone standing by the side of the cart track to Khojipura station.	III.	
32	"	"	An inscribed stone post said to have been found in the old enclosure wall of the village and now set up near the modern Rama temple in the village.	III.	
33	"	"	Another inscribed stone post near the temple.	III.	
34	"	"	A <i>sati</i> stone in <i>chhatri</i> on the west of village with an inscribed post planted near the steps.	II.	
35	Rameshwar.	"	A sculptured and inscribed memorial post (wornout) said to have been recovered from the bed of the river Chambal now planted near one of the modern temples.	I II	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Gird.					
1	Gwalior Fort.	In a niche near the Takasaligate ...	2	Nagari.	Hindi.
2	"	On a lintel in the Chaturbhuj Temple outside.	7	Old "	Sanskrit.
3	"	On the Chaturbhuj temple wall, inside ...	26	"	"
4	"	In a niche between the Chaturbhuj temple and the Lakshmana gate.	6	"	"
5	"	On a pillar with a Jaina image near the big Gajasura-Vadha image.	2	Nagari.	Hindi.
6	"	On a Jaina image near Gajasura-Vadha image.	1	"	Sanskrit.
7	"	By the side of a Jaina image ...	23	"	"
8	"	On a verandah of the Tikonia tank ...	2	"	Hindi.
9	"	On another " " ...	2	"	Sanskrit
10	"	On Assi Khamba ...	4	"	(corrupt). Hindi.
11	"	On a pillar in front of Sas-Bahu Temple ...	3	"	"
12	"	On a stone-slab in the porch of Sas-Bahu Temple.	21	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.
13	"	" " " " ...	20	"	"
14	"	In Telika Mandir ...	4	Nagari.	Hindi.
15	"	" " " " ...	3	"	"
16	"	" " " " ...	3	"	"
17	"	" " " " ...	1	"	"
18	"	On a Jaina Tirthankara, right-side. Urwahi group.	23	"	Sanskrit (corrupt).

D.

Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
Dungar Singh.	V. S. 1516 (A. C. 1459).	Name of King Dungar Singh is only legible.	
...	V. S. 932 (A. C. 875).	This inscription and one that follows next record four donations to two temples at Gwalior.	Published <i>vide</i> Ep. Ind. vol I Page 154.
...	V. S. 933 (A. C. 876).	" " " "	"
...	...	Seems to be a verse in praise of Ganesa.	Mostly illegible.
...	...	...	Damaged and illegible.
...	...	Reads Sri Chandra (?) Nikasya.	...
...	V. S. 16 [7] 3	Seems to mention Bhattaraka Sri Bhanu-Kirtideva, Sri Subhakitideva and certain other names.	Damaged and hence illegible.
...	V. S. 1488?		Badly written and therefore illegible.
...	...	Mentions the name of a Tomara warrior, Mendra.	...
...	V. S. 1586 (A. C. 1529).	Mentions one Sahigajita	...
...	Phaguna Vadi 2, V. S. 1547 (A. C. 1490).		Damaged and illegible.
Mahipala.	V. S. :150 (A. C. 1993.)	Records the completion of the temple of Vishnu (Padmanatha—now popularly known as Sas-Bahu) and the arrangement of charitable institutions connected therewith by Mahipala.	The two slabs together make one inscription Published <i>vide</i> Ind. Ant Vol. 15 pp. 36.
Kachhapaghata	...		Badly written and illegible.
...	Magha Sudi 13 V. S. 1537 (A. C. 1480)		Records only date.
...	Wednesday Bhado Vadi 8, V. S. 1522 (A. C. 1465).		
...	V. S. 1522 (A. C. 1465).		Much damaged and illegible.
...	...	Rai Sabala Singh's name is only legible	...
...	Vaisakha Sudi 1, V. S. 1497 (A. C. 1440).	Names of certain Jaina Acharyas are legible such as, Devasena, Yasahkirti, Jayakirti, etc.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Incribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
		District Gird — (continued)			
19	Gwalior Fort	On a Jaina Tirthankara, -Adinatha right-side, Urwahi group	14	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).
20	,	On a Jaina Tirthankara, left-side Urwahi Group.	21	"	"
21	,	On an image of Chandraprabha, left-side, Urwahi group.	15	"	Sanskrit.
22	"	On an image of Mahavira, Urwahi group...	11	"	"
23	"	On a Jaina image, left-side, Urwahi gate...	12	"	"
24	"	" " " " " ...	13	"	"
25	"	" " " " " ...	8	"	" (corrupt).
26	"	On a Jaina image on the Marimata side ...	19	"	"
27	"	On a Jaina image on the Marimata side ...	5	"	"
28	"	" " of Shantinath " " ...	9	"	"
29	"	" " " " " ...	9	"	"
30	"	" " " " " ...	15	"	"

D.
Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	Vaisakha Sudi 7, V. S. 1497 (A. C. 1440).	Seems to record the installation of the image of Adinatha (on which this inscription is engraved). Also vaguely refers to construction of charitable wells and gardens.	
Dungar Singh.	...		Much damaged and illegible.
"	Monday Magha Sudi 8, V.S. 1510 (A. C. 1453).	Records the installation of the image by Karama Singh in the reign of Dungarendra Deva (Dungar Singh), a Tomara Raja of Gopachala (Gwalior Fort). It further, mentions names of certain Jaina Acharyas viz., Bhattaraka, Sri Gonakirtideva, Sri Yasakirtideva, Malayakirtideva, Gunabhadradeva etc.	
"	"	Records the installation of the image by a number of devotees whose names are mentioned.	
Kirti Singh.	Monday Magha Sudi 12, V.S. 1522 (A. C. 1465).		Badly written, illegible.
...	...		" "
Dungar Singh.	Wendsday Vaisakh Sudi 10, V.S. 1514 (A. C. 1457).	Records the excavation of a cave temple by a group of devotees mentioned by names, in the reign of Dungar Singh.	
Kirti Singh.	Wendsday Chaitra Sudi 7, V. S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Records the installation of a huge image of Yugadinath by Hemaraja who has been styled as Sanghadhipati. Mentions names of several Jaina Acharyas.	
...	V. S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).		Illegible.
Kirti Singh.	Wendsday Chaitra Sudi 7, V.S 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Records the installation of a huge Jaina image of Shantinath in the reign of Kirtisingh Deva.	
"	"	" " " " certain names of Jaina Acharyas are also mentioned.	
"	Chaitra Sudi 15, V. S. 1525 (A. C 1468).	Same as above.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Gird.—(concl.)					
31	Gwalior Fort.	On a Jaina image, Marimata side ...	4	Nagari.	Hindi.
32	"	" " " " ...	4	"	Sanskrit.
33	"	On a Jaina image, Marimata Group ...	12	"	"
34	"	" of Parsvanath " ...	9	"	"
35	"	" " " " ...	7	"	" (incorrect).
36	"	" " " " ...	1	"	Hindi.
37	"	" " " " ...	9	"	"
38	"	On an image of Parsvanath, Marimata Group...	14	"	Sanskrit.
39	"	" " " " " " ...	5	"	"
40	"	On an image on the Koteshwar side ...	7	"	"
41	"	" " " " " " ...	5	"	"
42	"	On an image on the Koteshwar side ...	8	"	"
43	"	On a lintel of a temple-porch, found built into a modern pavement.	6	Old Nagari.	"
44	"	" " " " " " ...	6	"	" (verse). "
Pohari Jagir.					
45	Bhatnavar. Pohari Jagir.	On a square stone-slab lying loose on a platform near a Jaina image.	38	"	Sanskrit.

D.

Noticed during the year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
31 ...	Kartika Vadi 9, V. S. 1580 (A. C. 1523).	Purport is not clear.	
32 Kirti Singh.	Thursday Chaitra Sudi 15, V.S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Purport is not clear. Refers to the reign of Kirti Singh son of Dungarendradeva Tomara of Gopachaldurga (Gwalior Fort).	
33 "	Thursday Chaitra Sudi 15, V.S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Kirtisingh Deva and his official Gunabhadra Deva are recorded.	
34 "	Wednesday Chaitra V. S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Records the installation of the image of Parsvanatha.	
35 "	V. S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).		Illegible.
36 ...	...		"
37 "	V. S. 1525 (A. C. 1468.)		"
38 ...	Thursday Chaitra Sudi 15, V.S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).		Damaged and illegible.
39 Kirti Singh.	Thursday Chaitra Sudi 15 V.S. 1525 (A. C. 1468).	Records the installation of Parswanath by the wife of Kusaraja, during the reign of Kirtisingh.	
40 Dungar Singh	V. S. 1527 (A. C. 1470).	Records the installation of a Jaina image.	Much damaged.
41 Kirti Singh.	V. S. 1531 (A. C. 1474).	This inscription and one that follows, together make one inscription for purport See No. 42.	
42 Kirti Singh.	V. S. 1531 (A. C. 1474).	This inscription and No. 41 above together complete the record. They record the installation of an image of Parsvanatha by a lady named Champa, in the reign of Kirtisingh.	
43 Rama Deva.	No date in the existing portion.	This record completes itself in more than two lintels. Others being not found, the record remains incomplete.	Museum. Gujri Mahal.
...	...	Totally damaged.	Removed to the Museum.

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Esagarh.					
46	Naderi.	On a slab found lying loose.	26	Old Nagari (badly written)	" (incorrect).
47	Garhi Kadwaha.	On a Stone-slab in the Garhi at Kadwaha village.	1	Nagari.	Hindi.
48	"	On a Stone slab in the Garhi	6	"	"
49	"	" " " ...	30	"	"
50	"	" " " ...	2	"	"
51	"	" " " ...	19	"	"
52	"	" " " ...	8	"	"
53	"	" " " ...	13	"	"
54	"	" " " ...	6	"	"
55	Kadwaha.	On a Stone slab in the Garhi	2	"	"
56	"	" " " ...	2	"	"
57	"	" " " ...	7	"	"
58	"	On a Sati-Stone " ...	7	"	"

D.
Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
Sultan Mahmud Shah Khilaji.	V. S. 1527 (A. C. 1470).	During the reign of the Sultan mentioned, Bhauvdeva, Son of Hari Singhdev dug out a well.	Removed to the Museum.
...	...	Only figures 400 are legible.	
...	V. S. 1499 (A. C. 1442).	Only a name Arjuna is legible ...	
Mahmud Khilaji.	Thursday Vaisakha Sudi 11, V.S. 1504 (A. C. 1447)	Records its construction several persons at different dates. Purport not clear.	Many broken lines.
...	V. S. 1499 (A. C. 1442.)	Names of Ronapala, his sons Jairaja and Arjun are only legible.	
...	Thursday Jestha Vadi 7, V.S. 1487.	Records names of Brahmanas of Patwaria Family <i>i. e.</i> , Haridas, his son Hari and Hari's son Gangadas and of a Kaistha Mohansingh and his son Vaidana of Ranthanbhor.	
Mahmud Khilaji.	Thursday Vaisakha Sudi 1, V. S. 1504 (A. C. 1547).	Refers to the reign of Sultan Mahmud Khilji. Further records several names	Purport is not clear.
"	"	" " and many more names with Samvat 1473.	
...	...	Records the name of Sonapala, Hamir and Paldeva.	
...	V. S. 1475 (A. C. 1418).	Records the names of Dhanaraja and his son Ratan.	
...	V. S. 1466 (A. C. 1409).	Records the name of Thirpal, son of Ratansingh.	
...	Thursday Vaisakha Sudi 11 V.S. 1504 (A. C. 1447) and V. S. 1479 (A. C. 1422).	Refers to the name of Thirpal.	
Dilawar Khan	V. S. 146 [-].	Records the construction of a Sati monument of Ravat Kusal's wife in the reign of Dilawar Khan.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Esagarh.—(contd.)					
59	Kadwaha.	On a Sati-Stone ...	7	Nagari.	Hindi.
60	"	In the temple No. 3 ...	4	"	"
61	"	On a slab in the temple No. 3 ...	3	"	"
62	"	" " " ...	5	"	"
63	"	" " " ...	4	"	"
64	"	" " " ...	5	"	"
65	"	On a slab in the temple No. 3 ...	4	"	"
66	"	" " " ...	7	"	"
67	"	" " " ...	5	"	"
68	"	" " " ...	3	"	"
69	"	" " " ...	5	"	"
70	"	" " " ...	3	"	"
71	"	" " " ...	3	"	"
72	"	" " No. 9 ...	1	"	"
73	Sakarra.	On a Sati-pillar near a tank ...	4	"	"

D.

Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	V. S. 1476 (A. C. 1419).		Damaged and illegible.
...	V. S. 1562 (A. S. 1509).		" "
...	V. S. 1587 (A. C. 1530).	It is a pilgrim's record.	"
...	Ashadha Sudi 3 V. S. 1381 ?	Records names of Brahamanas—Madhava, Keshava, etc.	"
...	Faguna Vadi 5 V. S. 1473 (A. C. 1416).	Records the name of a <i>Gumasta</i> at Parganas Ranod and Kadwaha.	"
...	Sunday, Sravana Sudi 5 V. S. 1162 (A. C. 1105).	Records certain names, but they are illegible.	"
...			Damaged and illegible.
...	Thursday Vaisakha Sudi V.S. 1450 (A.C. 1393) and V.S. 1380 (A. C. 1323).	Some charitable grant of land or money was made to a Brahamana Bhaghor of <i>Gautam Gotra</i> by a Pandit Ramdas Deva.	"
...		Much Damaged and illegible.	"
...		" " "	"
...	Sawana Sudi 4, V. S. 158 [1].	Records names, such as Harichand, Gopi, etc.	"
...	V. S. 1468 (A. C. 1411).	Illegible.	"
...		"	"
...	Thursday Arwina Sudi 2, V.S. 1134 (A. C. 1077).	Records only date and year.	"
...	Friday Magh Sudi 3, V.S. 1120 ?	Illegible.	"

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	
1	2	3	4	5	6	
District Esagarh.—(contd.)						
74	Sakarra.	On a Sati-pillar near a tank	...	7	Nagari.	Hindi.
75	"	" " "	...	9	"	"
76	"	On a sati-stone near mata's temple	...	4	"	"
77	"	" " "	...	9	"	"
78	"	" " "	...	4	"	"
79	"	" " "	...	5	"	"
80	"	" " "	...	4	"	"
81	"	" " "	...	8	"	"
82	"	" " "	...	2	"	"
83	"	" " "	...	2	"	"
84	"	" " "	...	4	"	"
85	"	" " "	...	7	"	"
86	"	" " "	...	16	"	"
87	"	" " "	...	11	"	"
88	"	" " near the temple	...	8	"	"

D.
Noticed during the Year 1927.28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	...	Much damaged and illegible.	
...	Kartika Sudi 15, V. S. 1554 (A. C. 1497).	Much damaged and illegible	
...	V. S. 1237 (A. C. 1180).	" " "	
...	...	" " "	
...	V. S. 1304 (A. C. 1247.)	Mentions the date as आषण वदि ६ सं० १३०४.	
...	"	Illegible.	
...	"	"	
Ram Deva.	Monday Chaitra Sudi 5 V.S. 1342 (A. C. 1285.)	Certain names are mentioned.	
...	V.S. 128 (1) ?	Illegible.	
...	V. S. 1281.	Only date is legible.	
...	Tuesday Sawan Vadi 6 V. S. 1304 (A. C. 1247).	Records the name of Kunwar Singh.	
...	Magh Vadi 11 V. S. 1377 (A. C. 1320).	Illegible.	
...	Thursday Chaitra Sudi 1 V. S. 1375 (A. C. 1318).	"	
Ram Deva.	Saturday Jeshtha Sudi 4 V.S. 1341 (A. C. 1284).	Refers to the name of Rama Deva.	
Sultan Mah- mud.	Magha Sudi 11, V. S. 1403 (A. C. 1346).	Refers to the reign of Sultan Mahmud.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Esagarh.—(concl'd.)					
89	Sakarra.	On a Sati-pillar near the temple ...	10	Nagari.	Hindi.
90	"	" " " " ...	"	"	"
91	"	" " " " ...	"	"	"
92	"	" " " " ...	"	"	"
93	"	" " " " ...	"	"	"
District Narwar.					
94	Dinara.	On a copying slab, Suraighat ...	4	"	"
95	"	On the floor of a Chhatri ...	8	"	"
96	"	" " another " ...	10	"	"
97	Karera.	In a mosque adjoining a tomb ...	2	Naksh.	Persian.
98	Narwar.	On a loose stone found near an old well to the east of the town. ...	22	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.
99	"	In Idgah, Narwar ...	3	Naksh.	Persian.
100	"	In Shahi mosque, Narwar ...	3	"	"
District Sheopur.					
101	Hasilpur.	On a small stone outside Sitaram Temple. ...	6	Nagari.	Hindi.
102	"	On a detached pillar near the steps of a Sati-Chhatri. ...	23	"	"
103	"	On a sati pillar to the east of Hasilpur Kalan. ...	4	"	"

D

Noticed during the Year 1927.28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	1501	Mentions Sultan Khilji of Malwa.	
...	1342	Not copied.	
...	1397	" "	
...	1375	" "	
...	V. S. 1400.	Refers itself to the Emperor Mohmmmed Tughlaq of Delhi. Records the Sati of a Brahman Zamindar.	
...	Undated.	Illegible.	
...	"	Much damaged and illegible.	
...	"	"	
Shahjahan.	"	Records the construction of the mosque by Syed Salar during the reign of Shahjahan.	
Gopala, the King of Nalapur (Narwar).	V. S. 1338 (A. C. 1281).	Records the construction of a step well and plantations of trees by Ashaditya, a Kayastha in the time of Gopala, a descendant of Chahada, the King of Nalapur.	Removed to the Museum.
Shah Alam Bahadur.	Undated.	Imam Khan, son of Himmat Khan got this Idgah constructed in the reign of Shah Alam.	
Aurangzeb.	Date illegible.	Records its construction in the reign of Aurangzeb by Ahmed Khan.	
...	Vaisakha Vadi 12, V. S. 1897 (A. C. 1840)	Illegible.	
Maharaj Daulatrao Scindia.	Thursdey Vaisakha Sudi V. S. 1879 (A. C. 1822) Saka 1744.	Records the construction of the sati pillar by Ghasiram.	
...	Phagun Vadi 10, V. S. 1507 (A. C. 1450).	Illegible.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
		District Sheopur.—(concl'd.)			
104	Hasilpur.	On a Stone-post outside Sitaram Temple.	18	Nagari.	Hindi.
105	Rameshwar.	On a Stone-post	8	"	"
106	"	On four faces of a carved but worn-out memorial-stone said to be recovered recently from the bed of the river Chambal.	...	"	"
107	"	On a Stone-post in front of a temple.	12	"	"
108	"	On a broken slab in a niche in the empty temple of Shiva.	13	"	"
		District Bhilsa.			
109	Bhilsa.	On a tomb-stone in the Gumbas makabara, upper face round the miharab.	1	Naksh.	Arabic.
110	"	" " " on the top of the miharab.	1	"	"
111	"	" " " on one side of the tomb.	1	"	Persian.
112	"	" " " on the other side "	1	"	"
113	"	" " " on the northern face of the tomb-stone.	1	"	"
114	"	On the southern face of the tomb-stone in the Gumbas Makbara.	1	"	"
115	"	On a Stone-post in front of Gandhi Gate...	3	Nastaliq.	"
116	"	On a Sati-pillar. Charan Tirtha ...	3	Nagari.	Hindi.
117	"	On another Sati-pillar, " " ...	7	"	"

D.

Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	Sundy Magh Sudi 10, V S. 1613 (A. C. 1556).	Records the construction of a resting place by Lakshmana, grandson of Maharaja Bhimasingh Tomara.	
...	Vaisakha Sudi 13, V. S. 1923.	Records the construction of a temple of Nrisinha and installation of the image by Bijesingh of Gauda family of Sheopur.	
...	...	Illegible.	Not copied.
Jaysji Rao Scindia,	V. S. 1937 (A. C. 1880).	Records the construction of a temple, a garden and a step-well by Lakhmi Chand.	
...	V. S. 1836 (A. C. 1779).	Much damaged and illegible.	
...	...	A quotation from <i>Quran</i> is inscribed.	
...	...	<i>Kalama</i> is inscribed hereon.	
...	...	One verse in Persian, undecipherable.	
...	...	"	
...	...	Mentions that the tomb is of one Rehamatullah, Lord of the east and King among princes.	
...	A. H. 893 (A. C. 1448).	Mentions the date Rajjah A. H. 893.	
...	...	Records a royal order prohibiting exaction of <i>begar</i> from <i>Kolis</i> . (Hindu-weaver class).	
...	Monday Vaisakha Sudi 15, V S. 1692 (A. C. 1635).	Records a sati.	
...	V. S. 1654 (A. C. 1597).	Illegible.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Bhilsa.—(conold.)					
118	Besnagar.	On the shaft of a broken pillar.	1	Brahmi.	Prakrit.
119	"	On a coping stone of a railing of a Buddhist Stupa.	1	"	"
120	"	On another " " " ...	1	"	"
121	"	On a cross bar ...	1	"	"
122	"	On a railing pillar ...	1	"	"
123	"	On a cross-bar of a railing ...	1	"	"
124	"	On a railing ...	1	"	"
125	"	" " " ...	1	"	"
District Esagarh.					
126	Chanderi.	On Idgah ...	7	Naksh.	Persian.
District Gird.					
127	Gwalior.	On Khandarakhan's mosque, prayer Hall over the central miharab.	1	Nastaliq.	Arabic.
128	"	" " on the northern miharab	2	"	Persian.
129	"	" " on the southern miharab	2	"	"
130	"	On the corner pillar on south-west of the tomb of Mohamed Ghaus.	6	"	Persian.
131	Antri.	On Jama Masjid ...	8	Naksh.	"

D.

Noticed during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7	8	9	10
...	...	Records setting-up of a Garudadhvaja by a son (name missing) of Gotami. The record is engraved on 8 sides of the pillar.	Published <i>vide</i> Ep. Ind. Vol. X App. 669.
...	...	Records donation. Text:—असमाय दानं.	
...	...	सोमदास-भिखुनो दानं. " [वत or वध] मानस भिखुनो	Ep. Ind. Vol. X App. 671.
..	...	Text:—असदेवस दानं.	
...	...	Text:—धर्मगिरिनो भिखुनो दा [न].	<i>vide</i> Ep. Ind. Vol. X, App. 673.
...	...	" समिकाय दानं.	
...	...	" नदिकाय प्रवजित [ता] य दानं.	Ep. Ind. Vol. X App. 674.
...	...	" Only some figures are read.	Ep. Ind. Vol. X App. 675.
..	...	Records the construction of the Idgah by Sher Khan during the reign of Sultan Gayas Khan Khilaji.	
..	...	<i>Kalama</i> is only written on it.	
Shah Jahan of Dehli.	In Chronogram A. H. 1068 (A. C. 1657).	Records the construction of the masque by Nasiri Khan, son of Khandara Khan in the reign of Shahjahan.	
"	"	" " "	
...	A. H. 1008 (A. C. 1599).	Is a pilgrim's record of Mohamed Masum, the celebrated calligraphist of Akbar's reign, who accompanied Akbar in his march to Deccan.	
Humayun.	A. H. 938 (A. C. 1531).	Records the repairs of the mosque by Yar Muhammad Khan.	

APPENDIX E.

Statement of Coins examined during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

No.	Name of dynasty and king.	Metal.	Number of coins examined.	REMARKS.
Indo-Greeks B. C. 300 to A. C. 100.				
1	Alexander the Great	Gold.	1	
2	Deodotos	"	2	
3	Euthydemos	"	3	
4	" with Agathokles	Silver.	...	
5	Eukratides	"	4	
6	Heliokles	"	4	
7	Antiaklidas	"	2	
8	Apoleodotus	"	3	
9	Menander	"	6	
10	Hermaios	"	3	
Indo-Parthians or Sakas B. C. 115 to A. C. 100.				
11	Venones with Spalahora	Copper.	1	
12	Spalahora with Spalagadama	"	1	
13	Azes II	Silver.	2	
14	Soter megas	Copper.	2	
Indo-Scythian or Kushan A. C. 70-200				
15	Kadphises II	Gold.	1	
16	Huvishka	"	1	
17	"	Copper.	1	
18	Vasudeva	"	1	
Gupta A. C. 335-480.				
19	Chandragupta	Gold.	4	
Nagas 4th century A. C.				
20	Kha Naga	Copper.	13	
21	Va Naga	"	14	

No.	Name of dynasty and king.	Metal.	Number of coins examined.	REMARKS.
Nagas 4th century A. C.—(contd.)				
22	Bhim Naga	Copper.	14	
23	Skanda Naga	"	13	
24	Brihaspati Naga	"	64	
25	Ganapati Naga	"	18,070	
26	Deva Naga	"	341	
27	Pun Naga	"	15	
28	Unidentified Naga	"	78	
29	Illegible and damaged Naga	"	37	
✓ Indo-Sessanian A. C. 600-900.				
30	Dramma	Silver.	1	
31	"	Billon.	307	
32	A new type somewhat resembling Adivaraha coins	"	215	
Chandellas of Bundelkhand 11th century A. C.				
33	Kirtivarma Deva	Gold.	1	
34	Sallakshana Varma Deva	"	1	
Kings of Kashmir 11th century A. C.				
35	Queen Didda	Copper.	1	
36	King Ananta	"	1	
Haihaya of Maha Kosala or Eastern Chedi 14th A.C.				
37	Srimat Prithvi Deva	Copper.	1	
38	" Pratapa Malla Deva	"	1	
2nd dynasty of Vijayanagar 16th century A. C.				
39	Krishna Raya	Gold.	1	
Gurkhali dynasty of Nepal 18th century A. C.				
40	Prithvi Vikrama	Gold.	1	
41	Do.	Silver.	1	
42	Sri Surendra Vikrama	"	1	
43	Sri Rajendra Vikrama	"	2	
44	Sir Desal Gir ?	"	1	

No	Name of dynasty and king.	Metal.	Number of coins examined.	REMARKS.
Early Sultans of Delhi A. C. 1193—1554.				
45	Sher Shah (Delhi)	Silver.	1	
Mughal Emperors of Delhi A. C. 1526-1800.				
46	Akbar the Great	Silver.	1	
47	Do. (Ahamadabad)	"	1	
48	Jahangir	"	1	
49	Shah Jahan (Surat)	"	1	
Nawab of Oudh A. C. 1800-1858.				
50	Muhammad Ali (Lucknow)	Silver.	1	
51	Amjad Ali	"	1	
52	Wajid Ali	"	1	
Miscellaneous.				
53	Southern Indian Bahamni	Gold.	2	
Total coins examined			19,248	

**Statement of Antiquities added to the Archaeological Museum during the
Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.**

No.	Find-spot.	District.	Name of antiquity.	Size.
Stone Images.				
1	Akajhiri.	Narwar.	A head of Hanumat (?)	He. x Br. 1'3" x 1'
2	Mamon.	Esagarh.	Lamp bearer (a female)	2'11" x 1'
3	"	"	Do.	2'8" x 9"
4	"	"	Do.	1'7" x 6"
5	Naderi.	"	Vamana (dwarf) Vishnu	1'10" x 2'2"
6	Pawaya.	Gird.	A trifoil ornament ...	2'5" x 2'3"
7	"	"	A two faced capital	3'6" x 2'
8	Suhania	Tonwarghar.	Agni ...	4'2" x 2'7"
9	"	"	Brahma	3'4" x 2'5"
10	"	"	Brahmani	3'3" x 2'4"
11	"	"	Indra	3'3" x 2'3"
12	"	"	Goddess seated on lotus	3'9" x 1'8"
13	"	"	Parvati	3'8" x 1'9"
14	"	"	Rama with Sita	3'3" x 2'2"
15	"	"	Siva	3'3" x 2'2"
16	"	"	Vayu	4'5" x 2'7"
17	"	"	Vishnu...	4'2" x 2'5"
18	"	"	Yama	4'1" x 2'6"
19	"	"	Lion	2'5" x 2'4"
20	"	"	A female	3'3" x 1'9"
21	"	"	Do.	4'2" x 1'10"
22	"	"	Do.	3'4" x 1'8"
23	"	"	Do.	4'2" x 1'10"
24	"	"	Do.	4' x 1'8"
25	"	"	Do.	3'9" x 1'10"

No.	Find-spot.	District.	Name of antiquity.	Size.
Stone Images.—(contd.)				
26	Subania.	Tonwarghar.	A female ...	3'2" × 1'8"
27	"	"	Do. ...	3'4" × 1'8"
28	"	"	Do. ...	4'3" × 1'
29	"	"	<i>Sadhus</i> ...	1'9" × 2'6"
30	"	"	A man and a woman ...	3'2" × 2'9"
Stone Inscriptions.				
31	Gwalior	Gird.	A stone lintel with inscription in Sanskrit	4'2" × 1'
32	"	Gird.	Another stone lintel with inscription in Sanskrit.	3'6" × 1'
33	Surwaya.	Narwar.	A stone inscription in Sanskrit dated V.S. 1341	2' × 1'10"
34	...	...	Impression of an inscription in Persian on the tomb of Muhammad Ghaus.	Written in Nastaliq characters.
Old paintings.				
35	...	...	A Maratha sardar with retinue ...	6½" × 4½"
36	...	...	A man playing on a guitar and a lady listening (a Ragini).	9" × 6½"
37	...	...	Siva and Parvati ...	9½" × 6"
38	...	...	A lady proud of her beauty ...	"
39	...	...	Radha Krishna ...	"
40	...	...	A king with his bufoon friend ...	11" × 8½"
41	...	...	A Muhammadan king in court...	1'1½" × 1½"
42	Bagh.	Amjhera.	Coloured copy of a newly discovered fresco	3'5" × 3'3"
43	"	"	Outline of a newly discovered fresco	"
Coins.				
44	to 121	...	Ancient coins of gold, silver, and copper ...	78 Numbers.

APPENDIX G.

List of Photographs taken during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh ...	Sculpture of Brahma (inscribed) ...	Half.	
2	"	Panoramic view of the Bagh caves (a) ...	"	
3	"	Do. (b) ...	"	
4	"	Do. (c) ...	"	
District Bhilsa				
5	Bhilsa ...	A Persian inscription on a pillar ...	Full.	
District Esagarh				
6	Chanderi ...	Bada Madarsa, view from south-east ...	Half.	
7	"	" " south-west ...	"	
8	"	Shahzadi-ka-Roza, view from south-east ...	"	
9	"	Kati Ghati ...	"	
10	Kadwaha ..	Chandla Madh temple ...	"	
11	Sakarra ...	A temple on the northern end of tank ...	"	
12	"	Another " " ...	"	
13	"	Group of two temples on the bank of tank facing north.	"	
14	"	Inscribed memorial pillar ...	"	
15	"	" " another ...	"	
District Gird.				
16	Antri ...	Tomb of Abul Fazl before conservation, general view from south-east.	Full.	
17	"	" " " north-east.	"	
18	"	" " " After conservation, from south-east	"	
19	"	" " " north-east.	"	
20	"	Alamgiri mosque, interior ...	"	
21	"	A Persian inscription on above mosque ...	"	
22	Gwalior ...	A Persian inscription on the tomb of Md. Ghaus...	Half.	
23	"	Tomb of Tansen near the above ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size	REMARKS.
District Gird.—(contd.)				
24	Archaeological Museum, Gwalior.	A Persian inscription from Chanderi	Full.	
25		Lion capital from Udaygiri	"	
26	"	A standing goddess	"	
27	"	Another Persian inscription from Chanderi	Half.	
28	"	Mughal painting from Ujjain... ..	Full.	
29	"	A painting having a Maratha Raja on horse-back with two attendants.	"	
30	"	A painting having a man playing on Vina and a female standing beside a tree etc.	"	
31	"	A superscribed painting showing a female worshipping snake-hooded god and his consort with attendants.	"	
32	"	Do Do a male and two females standing.	"	
33	"	Do Do a male and a female standing beside trees in a garden and a sage wearing a crown is sitting.	"	
34	"	Do Do A Raja seated	Half.	
35	"	A carved slab showing a hand-to-hand fight	Full.	
36	"	Man capital from Pawaya, front view	Half.	
37	"	Do Do back view	"	
38	"	'Vayu' from Suhania	"	
39	"	'Siva' seated on Nandi, from Suhania	"	
40	"	'Vishnu' from Suhania	"	
41	"	Brahma seated, from Suhania	"	
42	"	Yama standing, from Suhania	"	
43	"	Rama with Sita (?) ,,	"	
44	"	A couple, from Suhania	"	
45	"	A group of seated males, from Suhania	"	
46	"	Tri Ratna from Pawaya	"	
47	"	Lion attacking an elephant, from Suhania... ..	"	
48	"	Agni, from Suhania	"	
49	"	Indra,	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS
District Gird,—(concl'd.)				
50	Archæological Museum, Gwalior.	Brahmani, from Suhania ...	"	
51	"	Parvati ...	"	
52	"	Kamalasanā ...	"	
53	"	Female figure from Suhania ...	"	
54-62	"	" " " " " " ...	"	
63	"	An old Nagari inscription from Gwalior Fort	Full,	
64	Lashkar.	Chhatri of Mama Saheb Jadhav ...	"	
65	"	" " " " back-view ...	"	
66	"	" " " " side ...	"	
District Mandasor.				
67	Mandasor.	Sculpture of Siva ...	Half	
68	"	(Srawan-ki-Kawad) Torana pillar ...	"	
District Narwar.				
69	Mahua.	An old temple (inscribed) from south-east ...	"	
70	"	Sculpture of Kali ...	"	
71	Narwar.	An inscription of a step well near Narwar ...	Full	
72	Surwaya.	Monastery, general view from north-west...	"	
73	"	" " " north... ...	"	
74	"	" " " with temple No.1 ...	"	
75	"	" " " from west ...	"	
76	"	" another general view from north-west ...	"	
77	"	A miniature temple on the roof of Monastery ...	Half	
78	"	A horse shaped stone peg in the interior of Monastery.	"	
79	"	General view showing temple No. 1 and open-air Museum.	Full	
80	"	Do Do temples Nos. 1-2 ...	"	
81	"	Temple No. 1 from north-west ...	"	
82	"	" " another view from north-west ...	"	
83	"	" " from south-west ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
District Narwar.—(concl'd.)				
84	Surwaya	Temple No. 1. pillars	Full	
85	"	" „ details of pillars	Half	
86	"	" „ „ another view	"	
87	"	" „ sculpture of Vayu	"	
88	"	" „ sculpture of Vishnu	"	
89	"	" „ sculpture of Mahisbasurmardini	"	
90	"	" „ sculpture of Siva	"	
91	"	" Nos. 2 and 3 general view	Full	
92	"	" „ No. 2 from south-east	"	
93	"	" „ „ 2 sculpture of Surya	Half	
94	"	" „ „ 2 Gajasuravadha	"	
District Sheopur.				
95	Hirapur.	Chhatris of Rajas, general view	Half	
96	"	A Sati-stone	"	
97	Rameswar.	Panoramic view of river Chambal with boats	"	
98	"	Dak Bungalow and harbour, near the bank of the Chambal.	"	
District Ujjain				
99	Ujjain.	Panoramic view of ghats along the Sipra river	Full	
Miscellaneous.				
100	...	Model plan of a town in ancient times	"	
101	...	Plate showing coins of the Naga Rajas of Narwar from C. M. I.	Half	
102	Indore.	A view of the Devaguradia hill	"	
103	"	A modern temple on the Devaguradia hill	"	

APPENDIX H.

List of Lantern Slides made during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
District Amjhera			
1	Bagh ...	Buddhist caves, general view. ...	
2	"	Scene of sorrow, an outline from the fresco paintings ...	
District Bhilsa.			
3	Besnagar ...	Khambaba or Heliodoros pillar ...	
4	Gyaraspur ...	Bajramath temple, back view ...	
5	Udaygiri ...	Cave No. 1, door frame ...	
6	Udaypur ...	Udaypur temple, back view ...	
District Isagarh.			
7	Chanderi ...	Shahzadi-ka-Roza, interior view ...	
District Gird.			
8	Gwalior Fort ...	Sas Bahu temple, interior view ...	
9	" "	Gujari Mahal, exterior view ..	
10	Archæological Museum.	An image of Siva standing. ...	
11	" "	" " " ...	
12-15	" "	Inscription ...	
16	" "	Long live our Maharaja ...	
17	" "	H. H.'s bust (coloured) ...	
18	" "	" " " ...	
19	Pawaya	Excavation trenches, general view ...	
20-23	"	Antiquities unearthed in excavations ...	
24	"	Pieces of the lintel of a Torana gateway ...	
District Mandasor.			
25	Mandasor ...	Image of Siva in fort ...	
26	"	A pillar of a Torana or Srawan-ki-Kawad in fort ...	
27	Sondni ...	A pillar of Yasodharman's victory ...	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
District Mandasor.—(concl'd.)			
28	Sondni ... District Narwar.	A pillar of Yasodharman's victory (another view) ...	
29	Khayavda ...	A temple	
30	Kolara ...	Jama Masjid, interior view	
31	Surwaya ... Rajputana.	Temple No. 1	
Foreign territories.			
32	Abu ...	Dilwara temple, interior view	
33-35	"	" " " another).	
36	"	" " exterior view	
37	"	" " ceiling	
38	"	" " another view	
39	"	" " " "	
Nizam's Dominions.			
40	Ajanta ...	Verandah of a cave	
41	"	A dogaba in a cave	
42	"	Cave No. 1, interior	
District Nellore			
43	Amravati ...	Railing pillars	
Orissa.			
44	Bhuvanesvar ...	Anant Vasudeva temple	
45	"	Parashuramesvar temple	
Bengal.			
46	Calcutta, Indian Museum.	Image of a female from Besnagar	
47	"	The <i>bodhi</i> tree of Vipassi Buddha	
48	"	" " Kessapa from Nagod	
49	"	Lion capital Rampurwa	
50	"	The visit of king Prasenajita of Kosala to Buddha (Bhagavator Dhamachakam)	

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
	Rajputana.		
51	Chittorgarh ...	Jaina Kirti Stambha	
	Delhi		
52	Delhi ...	Asoka pillar	
	Allahabad.		
53	Garwah ...	Matsya Avatara, sculpture in relief	
54	Ittagi ...	Temple --	
55	Karli ...	The Chaitya cave, interior	
	Bundelkhand.		
56	Khajuraha ...	A temple	
57	"	"	
58	"	Another temple	
	Nizam's Domi- nions.		
59	Ellora ...	Ten Tala caves	
60	"	Indra-Sabha (Jaina cave) temple courtyard	
61	"	Do. Do. pillars	
62	"	Rameswar cave pillars	
	Madras.		
63	Mallapuram ...	A rock cut Ratha (seven pagoda)	
64	"	Mahishamardini	
	Gujarat		
65	Modhere ...	Surya temple	
	Sindh.		
66	Mohenjodaro excavations.	Bust of a human figure	
67	"	Three heads of human figures	
68	"	A human skeleton	
69	"	View of skeletons in a trench... ..	
70	"	A bath (?)	
71	"	View of a well and a drain	
72	"	View of streets between buildings	
73	"	View of block of buildings	

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
74	Mohenjodaro excavations.	A painted jar	
75	"	A painted vase	
76	"	A big earthen pot or burial urn	
Punjab.			
77	Harappa ...	Inscribed seal	
Sindh.			
78-86	Mohenjodaro ...	Clay seals inscribed	
87	"	A necklace	
88	"	Excavated area, general view... ..	
89	"	" deep diggings	
90	"	A map of contour	
91	Nasik ...	Gautamiputra Vihara Cave III	
92	Rumendi ...	A pillar	
93	Sanchi ...	Stupa No. 2	
94	Tanjore ...	A temple in fort	
95	Sindh ...	A map showing Situ chaeolithic civilization in Indian and Western Asia,	
Gujerat.			
96	Vadnagar ...	Kirtistambha	
Java.			
97	Borobudur ...	Descriptive relief from a Buddhist temple, Jataka in panels.	
98	"	Do. Do.	
99	"	Do. Do.	
100	Chandi Prambanan.	Decorative relief panels : scene from Ramayana ...	
101	" "	" " " " " "	
102	Belahan ..	Vishnu on Garuda	
103	Chandi Banon ...	Ganesa	
104	Chandi Kidol ...	Temple	
105	" mandut...	"	
106	" "	"	

APPENDIX. I.

List of Drawings made during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

S. No.	Locality.	Description.	Size.	REMARKS.
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Elevation of proposed framing of frescoes on facade of caves No. 4 and 5.	3' = 1"	Issued to constructor.
2	"	Detail of a pillar No. P. of cave No. 4.	1' = 1"	
3	"	A coloured painting copied from cave No. 4.	42" x 22"	In museum.
4	"	Outline of above painting	"	In museum.
District Bhilsa				
5	Udaygiri.	Reconstruction plan of Gupta temple ...	10" = 1"	Inked only.
District Gird.				
6	Gwalior.	The proposed plan and section of the chhattri of the Rani of Jhansi.	2' = 1"	Issued to constructor (in pencil)
7	"	Section of the proposed chhattri of the Rani of Jhansi.	"	"
District Mandasor.				
8	Sondni.	Plan of Yasodharman's Pillars ...	4' = 1"	Inked only.
9	"	Site plan of Yasodharman's pillars ...	10' = 1"	"
District Ujjain.				
10	Ujjain	Plan of Chauvis Khamba gate ...	6' = 1"	"
11	"	Proposed plan of new building for an archaeological museum.	12' = 1"	In pencil.

APPENDIX J.

List of Books added to the Office Library during the Year 1927-28, Samvat 1984.

Serial No.	Title.	REMARKS.
Archaeological Survey Reports and Memoirs.		
1	Arch. Surv. of India, Annual report 1924-25	Gratis.
2	Annual Report of the Arch. Surv. of Ceylon for 1925-26	"
3	Annual Report of the Archæological Department, Travancore for the year ending 31st March 1927.	"
4	Annual Report of the Mysore Archæological Department for the year 1926.	"
5	Arch. Surv. of India, Memoir No. 25 Basrelief of Badami by R. D Banerji, M. A.	"
6	Arch. Surv. of India, Memoir No. 30. Beginning of Art in Eastern India with special referenece to sculptures in the Indian Museum Calcutta by R. P. Chanda.	"
7	Arch. Surv. of India, Memoir No. 32. Fragments of a Prajnāparamita manuscript from Central India by B. B. Bidyabinod.	"
8	Antiquities of Indian Tibet Part II by A. H. Francke	"
Art and Architecture.		
9	The music of India by Atiya Begum Fyzee Rahaman	Purchased.
10	The Bagh Caves published by the Archæological Department, Gwalior and India Society, London.	Gratis.
11	History of Indian and Indonesian Art by Dr. A. K. Coomarswamy.	Purchased.
12	Indian Architecture according to Manasara by P. K. Acharya.	"
13	A Dictionary of Hindu Architecture by P. K. Acharya	"
14	Indian Art and letters Vol. 1, No. 2 for 1927, published by the India Society, London.	"
15	Chalukyan Architecture by H. Cousins	Gratis.
Dictionary.		
16	Pocket Oxford Dictionary by F. G. Fowler	Purchased.
Epigraphy.		
17	Epigraphia Indica Vol XVIII July, 1926	Gratis.
18	Epigraphia Indo Moslemica 1923-24 by G. Yazdani, M. A.	"
19	Kharosthi inscriptions Part II by Sir Aurel Stein	"
20	Epigraphia Indica Vol. XIX Part I, January 1927	"

Serial No.	Title.	REMARKS.
21	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVII, Part VII, October 1928 ...	Gratis.
22	The Bakshali Manuscript, Parts I & II by G. K. Kaye ...	"
23	Muslim Calligraphy in the Ghosh collection, Calcutta by M. Mahfuz-ul-Haq, M. A.	Purchased.
Books and Bibliography.		
24	Supplement to the catalogue of books, Part II. in the Secretariat General Library at Motimahal.	Purchased.
25	Do to the Part I. Do. ...	"
History.		
26	India's past by A. A. Macdonell ...	Purchased.
27	History of Indian Philosophy, Vol. II by R. D. Ranade & S. K. Belvalker	"
28	The Aravidu dynasty of Vijayanagar Vol I, 1542-1614 by Rev. Henry Heras	"
29	The glories of Magadha by Prof. J. N. Samadar...	"
30	शिव भारत by स. म. दिवेकर ...	"
31	शिवचरित्र प्रदीप by आपटे व दिवेकर ...	"
32	जयराम कवि विरचित पर्णाल पर्वत ग्रहणारूपाय ...	"
33	भारतवर्ष का इतिहास महाभारत काल से लेकर प्राग्वेदिक काल तक का राजतिलक, सामाजिक व सम्पत्ता का इतिहास by Prof. Ram Devji.	"
34	भारतवर्ष का इतिहास (वैदिक तथा आर्षपर्व) by Prof. Ram Devji ...	"
35	A History of village communities in Western India by A. S. Altekar ...	"
Guides.		
36	A Guide to the Qutab, Delhi by J. A. Page ...	Gratis.
37	The commercial and industrial directory of the Gwalior State, for 1927 ...	"
Journals and Periodicals.		
38-50	Indian Antiquary from July 1927 to July 1928...	Purchased.
51	Index to Vol LVI-1927 of Indian Antiquary ...	"
52-63	Modern Review from July 1927 to June 1928 ...	"
64-66	The Indian Historical Quarterly Vol III, Nos. 2, 3 and 4 for 1927 ...	"
67	Do. Vol IV, No. 1 for March 1928 ...	"
68	Journal of the Bombay branch of the Royal Asiatic Society, Vol. III, Nos. 1 and 2.	"

Serial No.	Title.	REMARKS.
69—70	त्यागमुनि खंड १ अंक ५ व ६ ...	Purchased.
71—73	„ „ २ „ १—३ ...	„
74—77	नागरी प्रचारिणी पत्रिका भाग C अंक १—४ ...	„
78	The Quarterly Journal of the Andhra Historical Research Society, Vol. I, Part. IV, April 1927.	Purchased.
79	Do. Vol. II, Part I, July 1927 ...	„
80	Do. Vol. II, Part II, October 1927 ...	„
81—84	The Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XIII, Nos. 1, 2, 3 and 4	„
Literature.		
85	Mahabharata by V. S. Sukhtankar, PH. D. ...	„
86	Avataras by Mrs. Annie Besant ...	„
87	Manu's land and trade law by R. Vidyanath Ayyar ...	„
88	Kanade passages in the Axyrhynous papyri No. 413 ...	„
89	नादीय सूक्त भाष्य by श. रा. राजवाडे ...	„
Miscellaneous.		
90	The Indian Year Book 1928 ...	„
91	Sir Asutosh Memorial Volume ...	„
92	Hindutva by a Maratha ...	„
93	Madho Rao Scindia of Gwalior by Messrs Haksar and Bull ...	„
94	Indian after-dinner stories Vo. II by A. S. P. Ayyar ...	„
95	The lady of the lotus (Rupamati, queen of Mandu) by Ahmad-ul-Umri Turkoman.	„
96	Proceedings and translations of the 4th Oriental Conference Vol. I ...	Free.
97	The Times of India, illustrated weekly Nos. for June 15, 1928 ...	Purchased.
98	Do. Do. January 22, 1928 ...	„
99	Do. Do. „ 29, 1928 ...	„
100	Do. Do. February 5, 1928 ...	„
Photography.		
101	Manual of photography (Ilford) ...	„
102	How to make good pictures published by Kodak...	„

Serial No.	Title.	REMARKS.
103	Elementary photographic chemistry... ..	Purchased.
104	The fundamentals of photography	"
105	List of Archaeological photo negatives of Bihar and Orissa, Central Provinces and Berar, upto the year 1926 by Page.	Gratis.
106	List of photo negatives of Assam and Bengal by Mr. Dikshit	"
Museum.		
107-112	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts from February 1926 to December 1926 Six numbers.	Purchased.
113-115	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts from February 1927 to June 1927. Three numbers.	"
116	Do. for December 1927	"
117	Do. for February 1928	"
118	Do. for April 1928... ..	"
119	Exhibition of antiquities discovered by the Archaeological Department, during the year 1926-27.	Gratis.
State Publications.		
120	Selections of Council's orders for Samvat 1882	Free.
121	Annual Civil list upto June 1927	Purchased.
122	Motorists' Road guide to Gwalior State	"

APPENDIX K.

Statement of Income realised during Samvat 1984.

Serial No.	Head.	Amount.	REMARKS.
1	By sale of books ...	Rs. 152 11 5	
2	By sale of tender forms ...	8 0 0	
3	By sale of photographs ...	4 4 0	
4	Miscellaneous ...	1 5 3	
	Total ...	166 4 8	

APPENDIX L.

Statement of Expenditure incurred in Samvat 1984.

Serial No.	Head.	Amount current year.			Amount last year.			Total amount.		
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.
1	Salaries	9,992	2	5	...			9,992	2	5
2	Travelling allowances	2,725	2	8	...			2,725	2	8
3	Contingencies	1,499	1	10	121	4	0	1,620	5	10
4	Books and Periodicals	319	4	0	9	15	0	329	3	0
5	Miscellaneous head	468	8	3	...			468	8	3
6	Publication	310	4	0	152	11	6	462	15	6
7	Museum	2,309	9	0	...			2,309	9	0
8	Conservation, excavation etc., etc.	3,866	6	8	114	5	0	3,980	11	8
	Total	21,490	6	10	398	3	6	21,888	10	4
9	Expenditure over and above budget grant.	129	14	9	...			129	14	9
10	Special grant for Bagh Caves	...			14,939	2	6	14,939	2	6
11	Special grant for Bagh monograph	...			3,131	2	3	3,131	2	3
	GRAND TOTAL	21,620	5	7	18,468	8	3	40,088	13	10

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, interior view from n.-e.
during repairs.

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, interior view from n.-e.
before repairs.

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, interior view from s.w. before repairs.

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, interior view from s.w. during repairs.

(a) Hindu Monastery at Surwaya, with later accretions.

(b) Hindu Monastery at Surwaya, freed from later accretions.

(a) Tomb of Abul Fazal at Antri, after conservation.

(b) An old painting (a ragini.)

(b) A miniature shrine on top of Monastery at Surwaya.

(a) Siva Temple at Mahua.

(a) A double faced capital from Pawaya, one face.

(b) A double faced capital from Pawaya, the other face.

(c) Brahma from Bagh.

(d) Vishnu from Suhania.

(a) Indra from Suhania.

(b) Agni from Suhania.

(c) Yama from Suhania.

(d) Vayu from Suhania.

(a) Kamalasana from Suhania.

(b) Brahmani from Suhania.

(c) A standing goddess from Suhania.

(d) Another standing goddess from Suhania.

2

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